

European Public Local Authorities' Network for driving
the Energy Transition

**D2.2 - REPORT ON EXISTING GOVERNANCE
STRUCTURES AND LIST OF AVAILABLE
TOOLS FOR THE MONITORING OF
ENERGY TRANSITION PROJECTS**

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Executive summary

ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to develop and implement a methodology to enhance and facilitate multi-level governance for energy transition in public authorities and the coordinated adoption of Energy Transition Measures for achieving the European sustainability targets.

This document presents a desk review of existing governance networks, projects and initiatives, at local and regional level in the pilot territories as well as at national/EU level, aiming to improve multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of Energy Transition (ET) projects by public authorities. The purpose of the review was to identify best practices, barriers and lessons learnt, that could be linked to and contribute to the aims of ePLANET, whereby new figures/structures and tools will be proposed, to improve vertical and horizontal governance for energy transition.

Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CCR	Carbon Climate Registry
CDP	Carbon Disclosure Project (non-profit charity that runs the global disclosure system to manage environmental impacts)
CEMR	Council of European Municipalities and Regions
CETA	Clean Energy Transition Agenda
CIMNE	International Centre for Numerical Methods in Engineering
CRES	Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving
CoM	Covenant of Mayors
DDGI	Girona Provincial Council
DSO	Distributor System Operator (Utility Company)
DL	Decree Law
EAZK	Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
EE	Energy Efficiency
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESCO	Energy Service Company
ET	Energy Transition
GCoM	Global Covenant of Mayors
ICAEN	Catalan Institute for Energy
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
ISEAP	Island Sustainable Energy Plan
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan(s)
NSRF	National Strategic Reference Framework
NZEB	Nearly Zero Energy Buildings
NUTS	Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
PA	Public Authority(ies)
RAP	Regional Action Plan
RD	Royal Decree
RDFC	Regional Development Fund of Crete
RDL	Royal Decree Law
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SAC	Strategic Advisory Committee
SE(C)AP	Sustainable Energy (and Climate) Action Plan
SMAP	Sustainable Mobility Action Plan

1 Background

The ePLANET project (“European Public Local Authorities’ Network for driving the Energy Transition”) is implemented in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Programme. The project consortium includes 10 partners from 6 EU countries: Spain, Greece, Belgium, Germany, Czech Republic, France, and the Lead Partner is CIMNE (International Centre for Numerical Methods in Engineering). The project has a duration of 36 months.

The overall objective of the project is to develop and implement a methodology to enhance and facilitate the energy transition **multi-level governance of public authorities**, aiming at the formulation of a **coordinated strategy and energy transition plans**, to facilitate the achievement of European sustainability targets.

The **Regulation on the Governance of the Energy Union** (EU 2018/1999) (part of the Clean Energy for all Europeans package) requires the Member States to develop integrated National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) covering a ten-year period from 2021 to 2030, EU and national long-term strategies, as well as implement integrated reporting, monitoring and data publication. The NECPs determine the sustainable energy roadmaps and action plans that regional and local authorities define and deploy in their territories. The Regulation foresees that Member States shall establish a **multi-level climate and energy dialogue**, following up on previous recommendations in the Committee of the Regions “White paper on Multi-level Governance” (2009/C211/01) which established Governance as “one of the main keys to the success of the process of European integration” and stressed the need for establishing effective **multi-level governance** as a “coordinated action by the European Union, the Member States and local and regional authorities, based on partnership and aimed at drawing up and implementing EU policies”.

ePLANET’s primary aim is to improve horizontal and vertical integration of the Energy Transition plans at different governance levels and their monitoring and synchronisation with the EU objectives. The governance methodology of ePLANET relies on the concept of local governance clusters / networks and the deployment of governance facilitators, such as public advisors on energy transition. Those figures will be central to the interaction between public authorities.

To address the above, the project includes a dedicated **Work Package 2 (“Governance”)**, coordinated by partner ICAEN (Catalan Energy Institute), which includes a number of activities related to identifying the needs and gathering requirements for improving governance coordination among public authorities and stakeholders, reviewing the existing governance status in the partners’ territories, existing networks and relevant projects, and defining new structures and tools to support the public authorities towards energy transition in an integrated approach between all governance levels.

2 Introduction

The main objectives of the ePLANET **Work Package 2 (“Governance”)** are the following:

- To identify necessities and gather requirements for improved (horizontal and vertical) governance coordination among Public Authorities (PA) and key stakeholders in energy transition planning and monitoring;
- To classify energy transition policies, strategies and measures on the basis of previous and existing local, regional and national plans, projects and actions;
- To define new structures and figures to support the energy transition and the links between energy transition plans at the different governance levels (local, regional, national);
- To define a framework and procedures for monitoring and evaluating the progress in energy transition.

This report was developed in the framework of **Task 2.2 (“Governance networks”)**, the objective of which is to undertake a desk review, gathering and analysing requirements and best practices from existing EU or national governance networks and initiatives and from past / ongoing projects addressing public authorities’ Energy Transition (ET). The review focused on the following aspects:

- **Current legal and policy framework** related to energy transition in the partners’ territories (national and /or regional and /or local level);
- **Governance status** related to energy transition in **current EU-wide networks and initiative** (governance structures and tools /methodologies /digital platforms introduced by these networks for coordinating and monitoring energy transition plans and projects);
- **Governance status** related to energy transition in the **3 ePLANET pilot territories** (existing governance structures and tools/methodologies/digital platforms currently used by public authorities for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of energy transition plans and projects);
- **Best practices** on multi-level governance for energy transition (governance structures and /or tools /methodologies /digital platforms), identified **from past or ongoing projects** of the consortium partners and beyond.

The outcomes of this review aim to provide an overview and better understanding of the current governance framework in the partners’ territories, identifying best practices, barriers and lessons learnt from past and ongoing EU and national projects and initiatives. The review will also feed subsequent WP2 Tasks, such as T2.4, where new figures/structures and tools will be proposed by ePLANET, to improve vertical and horizontal governance for energy transition.

3 Involved partners

The following sections provide short profiles of the project partners that were involved in the preparation of this report:

PP03 - Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES)

CRES is based in Athens, in the Region of Attica (Greece). It is the Greek national centre for Renewable Energy Sources (RES), Rational Use of Energy (RUE) and Energy Saving (ES). It is also appointed by Law as the National Coordinating Centre in Greece for supporting the implementation of national policy for improving energy efficiency, including energy-efficiency in buildings, and the promotion of RES. It offers technical support to the Ministry of Environment and Energy as well as to public entities at regional and local level, for developing and implementing energy renovation plans and projects for public buildings. CRES is also the National coordinator of the Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy, providing technical support to local authorities for developing and implementing their sustainable energy action plans.

Its main roles in the ePLANET project include: Coordination of Tasks 2.2, 3.5; Coordination of WP6; Technical support to the RDFC for WP3 pilot activities; Transferring activities at national level.

PP01 - International Centre for Numerical Methods in Engineering (CIMNE)

CIMNE is based in Barcelona, in the Region of Catalonia (Spain). It is a leading research and technological development institution with a proven ability to deliver big data management services in energy, building and environment fields.

In ePLANET, CIMNE is the project coordinator, technology provider and responsible for the ePLANET platform development. The EU project ePLANET is a logical progress of CIMNE BEE Group's dedicated department, providing innovative solutions for local public authorities to drive them in the Energy Transition.

Its main roles in the project include: Project coordinator; Responsible of WP1, WP3; Coordination of Tasks 2.3, 2.5.

PP02 - Catalan Institute for Energy (ICAEN)

ICAEN is based in Barcelona, in the Region of Catalonia (Spain). It is the entity of the Government of Catalonia responsible for developing and carrying out the Catalan energy policy, especially in the field of energy efficiency and renewable energies. ICAEN develops programs to promote RES and energy efficiency in all economic sectors: industry, transport, primary and buildings. ICAEN is in charge of buildings Energy Performance Certification in Catalonia and leads the Energy Efficiency Plan of the Catalan Government buildings. In addition, ICAEN is involved and works jointly with the local community in the development of energy efficiency actions in municipal buildings, public lighting and efficient mobility.

Likewise, ICAEN collaborates with other Ministries of the Catalan Government to develop transversal actions such as the National Agreement for the Energy Transition of Catalonia, the Action Plan for Energy Efficiency in Industry, the Catalan Strategy for Energy Renovation of Buildings or the Biomass Strategy.

Its main roles in the ePLANET project include: Coordinator of WP2 (Governance); support to the rest of the tasks; Participation in Capacity building and training in Municipalities of Catalonia; Dissemination at a local level of project outputs.

PP04 - European Federation of Agencies and Regions for Energy and Environment (FEDARENE)

FEDARENE is based in Brussels (Belgium). FEDARENE is the premier European network of regional and local organisations which implement, co-ordinate and facilitate energy and environment policies. Regional and local agencies, regional governments and departments working in these fields, are represented in FEDARENE.

Its main roles in the ePLANET project include: EU wide replication; Organisation of stakeholder engagement activities; Coordination of WP5.

PP05 - ICLEI Local Governments for Sustainability (ICLEI EURO)

ICLEI is based in Freiburg im Breisgau, in Germany. It is a global network working with more than 2,500 local and regional governments committed to sustainable urban development. Active in 125+ countries, ICLEI influences sustainability policy and drives local action for low emission, nature-based, equitable, resilient and circular development. Its Members and team of experts work together through peer exchange, partnerships and capacity building to create systemic change for urban sustainability.

Its main roles in the ePLANET project include: Supporting continuous engagement, feedback and project EU-wide replication; Leading Task 6.2 and responsible for D6.3 and D6.4; Contributing to all WPs.

PP06 - Girona Provincial Council (DDGI)

Diputació de Girona (Girona Provincial Council) is based in Girona, in the Region of Catalonia (Spain). It is the public local authority for the Girona province and provides technical, financial and administrative support to all the 221 Municipalities within its operational area. It is a Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy Coordinator and one of their main stakeholders in the province of Girona. It supports all municipalities to sign, join and develop their own Sustainable Energy (and Climate) Action Plan.

Its main roles in the ePLANET project include: Coordination of the pilot application in the pilot region of Girona province; Contribution to all Work Packages, with a special focus on the multi-level regional governance (WP2) and the scaling-up to the whole region and replication activities (WP6).

PP07 - Regional Development Fund of Crete (RDFC)

RDFC is based in the city of Heraklion, in the Region of Crete (Greece). It is a public entity under private law, established in February 1998 and it was assumed an important role in the implementation of an innovative institution, aimed at supporting Regional Development of the elected (2011) Regional authorities and the process of decentralization in Greece. Under the RDFC, operates the Regional Energy Agency of Crete (REAC), established in 1994 by the Region of Crete and the European Commission as one of the first Energy Regional Agencies in Europe and the first at regional level in Greece.

REAC is the Regional Coordinator-for the whole island of Crete-of the EU Covenant of Mayors initiative and a member of the Covenant of Islands.

Its main roles in the ePLANET project include: Coordination of the pilot application in the pilot region of Crete; Contribution to the multi-level regional governance (WP2) as the regional coordinator of the CoM and to all other WPs of the project.

PP08 - Energy Agency of the Zlín Region (EAZK)

EAZK is based in the City of Zlín, in the Zlín Region (Czech Republic). It is a non-profit organisation. It is a regional energy agency established in 2006 and 100% owned by the Zlín Region. EAZK was primarily established as an implementing tool of the Zlín Region energy policy.

EAZK operates within the whole area of the Zlín Region which is identical with NUTS 3-CZ072¹. The EAZK is a project partner with a great potential to address various target groups as the agency provides energy management for more than 150 organisations established both by the Zlín Region and particular municipalities.

Since 2014 EAZK has been Covenant of Mayor Supporter and takes action on territories of the Zlín Region in the field of energy to promote the Covenant of Mayors initiative and support municipalities in their effort to adapt their local level policy and goals to be in synergies with existing Covenant of Mayors goals.

Its main roles in the ePLANET project include: Representative of the Pilot Region (Zlín Region), coordinating the pilot implementation; Contribution to the Work Packages, with particular focus on the transferring activities (scaling up to the whole region, replication to other regions) but also on capacity building (user's empowerment, WP4), the definition and deployment of clustering groups and governance methodology, and the institutionalization of ePLANET outcomes.

¹ Eurostat NUTS classification: Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/background>

4 Methodology for information collection

CRES as the Task 2.2 responsible partner, prepared a 'T2.2 Template for Information collection' that formed the basis for the development of the present Deliverable. After peer-review of the Template by the project Lead Partner (CIMNE) and the WP2 coordinator (ICAEN), it was circulated to the Task contributing partners, who provided their feedback by completing the sections of the template that were relevant to their territories and their organisational context. In addition, a desk review and collection of relevant information were undertaken by CRES.

Information was collected on the following aspects:

- Legal and policy framework for energy transition at national /regional /local level in the partners' territories;
- Governance status in relation to energy transition, in current EU-wide networks and initiatives related to the project objectives;
- Governance status within the pilot territories as regards energy transition;
- Best practices on multi-level governance for energy transition, identified from past or ongoing projects of the partners and beyond (national / EU projects).

The 'T2.2 Template for Information collection' is included in the Appendix of this report.

5 Review of existing ET governance framework, networks and projects

The sections that follow present the outcomes of the review that was undertaken, of the existing governance framework for energy transition in the partners' territories, in terms of legal and policy framework, current requirements and governance figures and/or tools introduced by existing EU-wide networks and national initiatives, current governance structures and / or tools / platforms already used by public authorities in the pilot territories to coordinate and monitor energy transition projects, and relevant best practices identified from past and ongoing projects.

5.1 Legal and policy framework for energy transition

The following tables present a review of the key elements of the current **legal and policy framework (at national and / or regional pilot level and / or local level)** related to **energy transition** in the partners’ territories, including:

- Current laws for the transposition of the most relevant European Directives related to energy transition (e.g. 2010/31/EU, 2012/27/EU, 2018/844/EU etc.);
- Any specific policies, regulations, or measures adopted for the implementation of the aforementioned legal framework;
- Any existing energy transition plans at national and/or regional pilot level and/or local level in the partners’ territories (e.g. National Energy & Climate Plans, regional energy transition plans, local Sustainable Energy & Climate Action Plans etc.).

The main objectives of the provided elements are described and the governance level (national, regional or local) to which each element applies. Also, the implementation status, any lack of policies, or possible barriers in the implementation of the legal / policy framework.

5.1.1 Greece / Region of Crete

No. of Element	1
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Law 4122/2013 on the Energy Efficiency of Buildings - Transposition of the recast EPBD directive 2010/31/EU into the Greek legislation
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	<p>The legislation addresses energy efficiency of new and renovated buildings. It put into force the requirement for the definition of the cost-optimal levels of the minimum energy performance requirements following the supplementary EU regulation 244/2012 (methodology for the determination of cost-optimal levels).</p> <p>It put into force the requirement for Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (NZEBs):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From 1.1.2019 all new public buildings should be NZEB • From 1.1.2021 all new buildings should be NZEB. <p>It put into force the requirement to prepare National plan for increasing the number of NZEBs, and set out the methodology for</p>

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	calculating buildings' energy performance and issuing Energy Performance Certificates. It introduced the concept of "smart readiness" of buildings.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p><u>Progress:</u></p> <p>The Law introduced (in 2013) an updated methodology for calculating the energy performance of buildings and introduced the requirement for NZEB levels for new and refurbished buildings. The Greek Buildings Energy Regulation (KENAK) was updated in 2017, to incorporate the provisions of the Law, along with revised Technical Guidelines to detail the implementation methodology. The National plan for increasing the number of NZEBs, including among others, the definition of NZEBs for new and refurbished buildings, was issued later (in 2018).</p> <p><u>Barriers-delays:</u></p> <p>Delays in the Regulation update and missing clear definition of the term "NZEB" until 2018, has led to delays in the implementation of the provisions of the Law, thus delays in the preparation of NZEB projects in the public and private sector.</p>
References	<p>L. 4122/2013 url-GR: https://www.buildingcert.gr/N4122_2013.pdf</p> <p>Concerted Action EPBD - Implementation of the EPBD Greece (2020), url-ENG: https://epbd-ca.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/Implementation-of-the-EPBD-in-Greece-2020.pdf</p>

No. of Element	2
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Law 4342/2015 on Energy Efficiency - Transposition of the EED directive 2012/27/EU into the Greek legislation
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	The legislation introduced the requirements for the exemplary role of public buildings. It put into force the requirement for the formulation of a National Energy Efficiency Action Plan that constitutes a policy tool for the development of a strategy to improve energy efficiency (in buildings and other sectors).

	<p>It introduced the requirement for producing a National long-term strategy for renovation of the building stock (residential and commercial, public and private).</p> <p>It put into force the obligation for a 3% of floor-area annual renovation (starting from 1.1.2014) of buildings owned and occupied by the central government (above 250m²), towards complying with the legislation minimum energy performance requirements.</p> <p>It put into force the obligation for regional and local public authorities, for buildings under their jurisdiction, to:</p> <p>(a) Conduct Energy Efficiency plans for the improvement of the energy efficiency of their public-building stock, to be monitored, updated and submitted to the Ministry of Environment and Energy every 2 years;</p> <p>(b) Apply an energy management system including energy audits;</p> <p>(c) Where feasible, take advantage of innovative financial schemes, including energy performance contracting (ESCOs), for the implementation of the energy upgrading projects foreseen in the Energy Efficiency plans.</p> <p>Buildings included in Energy Efficiency plans at regional and local level have priority in being eligible for financial incentives and programmes.</p>
<p>Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)</p>	<p><u>Progress:</u></p> <p>Initially completed catalogue of 82 governmental priority buildings for 3% annual renovation, subsequently replaced by catalogue of 21 buildings.</p> <p><u>Barriers-delays:</u></p> <p>Few public-buildings energy-efficiency plans are produced so far by local and regional authorities, mainly because such plans still remain a simple grading (rather than ON/OFF) criterion in most of the relevant funding Programmes.</p>
<p>References</p>	<p>L. 4342/2015 url-GR: https://www.buildingcert.gr/files/FEK_143A_2015.pdf</p> <p>Concerted Action EED - Implementation of the EED in Greece (2021), url-ENG: https://www.ca-eed.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/CA_EED_report_GREECE.pdf</p>

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No. of Element	3
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Law 4685/2020 - Transposition of directive 2018/844/EU into the Greek legislation (amending 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings and 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency)
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	The Law updates articles of L.4122/2013 and L.4342/2015. It introduces incentives to support buildings renovation towards NZEB. It puts into force that from 01/06/2021, for the construction permit of a new building, the submission of an Energy Performance Study is required to demonstrate that the building meets the energy performance and minimum standards of a NZEB building.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<u>Barriers-delays:</u> In many cases, energy consultants realised that it is difficult to achieve NZEB standards (energy class A for new buildings, B+ for refurbished buildings) and as a result there were delays in the issuing of construction permits.
References	L. 4685/2020 url-GR: https://ypen.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/4685_2020_FEK92A_ar57_71_113N4342.pdf

No. of Element	4
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Law 4513/2018 on Energy Communities
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	The Law provides Greek public authorities with the right to participate in energy communities producing, storing, distributing and supplying their own energy through the use of renewable energy sources (RES) and energy efficiency measures (EE).

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	<p>According to Law 4513/2018, public authorities are provided with the right to participate in energy communities at a share of up to 40% (50% on islands). This law thus constitutes an essential policy tool for Municipalities in meeting their SEAP targets but also in reducing their energy costs (for street lighting, public buildings, waste management, etc.), improving EE in their infrastructure and fighting energy poverty via the supply of low-cost energy.</p> <p>The overarching goal is to increase the use of RES and EE in Greek Municipalities through their participation in energy communities thereby contributing to the reduction of greenhouse gases (GHG), the fight against energy poverty and the promotion of social economy and welfare.</p>
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p><u>Progress:</u></p> <p>In total in Feb.2022, 949 energy communities are included in the national register.</p> <p><u>Barriers-delays:</u></p> <p>Even though Greek Municipalities dispose of significant RES/EE potential and L.4513/2018 promotes their participation in Energy Communities, progress has been slow in forming energy communities, due to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of know-how and expert counselling of governors and mayors • Lack of skills and capacities of municipal employees • Low level of citizens' awareness
References	<p>L. 4513/2018 url-GR: https://adminportal.acci.gr/images/N_F1669710387.4513.2018.pdf</p> <p>Statistics on Energy Communities in Greece (Feb.2022): https://encremenco.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/stats-feb-2022.pdf</p>

No. of Element	5
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Law 4710/2020 on the Promotion of e-mobility - Transposition of directive 2019/1161/EU into the Greek legislation
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National

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Description / key aspects	<p>The purpose of this Law is the promotion of the use of electric vehicles, the development of publicly accessible recharging infrastructure and the formation of a full-fledged regulatory framework for the e-mobility market.</p> <p>The Law includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General rules and incentives for the promotion of e-mobility. • Tax incentives related to the purchase, leasing and use of electric vehicles. • Regulations for the organization and operation of the e-mobility market. <p>Urban planning regulations apply for the installation of charging stations and spatial planning regulations for the development of publicly accessible charging stations</p>
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p><u>Progress:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsidies for the purchase of electric vehicles. • Subsidies and tax exemptions for companies • Replacement of the vehicle fleet in Municipalities (25% of new vehicles are expected to be electric, form 08/2021) <p><u>Barriers:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of infrastructure - few chargers in the road network • Distrust of this new technology
References	L. 4510/2020

No. of Element	6
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Law 4843/2021- Transposition of directive 2018/2002/EU into the Greek legislation, relating to “amending Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency, adapting to the provisions of the Regulation 2018/1999/EU on the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action, and to the provisions of Regulation 2019/826/EU on the contents of comprehensive assessments of the potential for efficient heating and cooling and related regulations for the energy efficiency in the building sector and for the promotion of Renewable Energy Resources and competition on the energy market”.
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	<p>Article 6 "Exemplary role of buildings belonging to the public sector".</p> <p>For local and regional authorities, an Energy Efficiency Plan for their building stock must be prepared, according to the template posted on the website of the Ministry of Environment and Energy, including:</p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The characteristics of the building stock • Prioritization of the building stock for energy renovation • Techno-economic analysis of energy renovation • A detailed plan for achieve a specific energy target <p>And must be submitted, until 31.12.2022, to the Ministry of Environment and Energy. The Plan is reviewed every four (4) years.</p>
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p><u>Progress:</u></p> <p>Few public-buildings energy-efficiency plans are produced so far by local and regional authorities. The Plan is mandatory for the participation of local/regional authorities in financial programs for energy upgrades of their buildings.</p> <p><u>Barriers-delays:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in data collection for public buildings • Missing methods for public buildings bundling and for decision making towards Building Energy Renovation projects • Insufficient capacity to attract funding
References	<p>L. 4843/2021</p> <p>https://ypen.gov.gr/energeia/energeiaki-exoikonomisi/ktiria/schedio-energeiakis-apodosis-ktirion-perifereion-kai-dimon/</p>

No. of Element	7
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	<p>National Energy and Climate Plan (2019)</p> <p>The Greek government’s strategic plan for climate and energy issues, setting out a detailed roadmap regarding the attainment of specific energy and climate objectives by 2030.</p>
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	<p>The NECP stresses Greece’s priorities and development potential in terms of energy and addressing climate change and aims to serve as the key tool for drawing up the national energy and climate policy in the next decade, taking into account the Commission’s recommendations and the UN sustainable development goals.</p> <p>The NECP sets out and details the individual policy priorities for the forthcoming period and the corresponding policy measures that are being planned for implementing the priorities and attaining the objectives of the NECP, under seven different themes:</p>

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	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Climate change, emissions and removals of greenhouse gases 2. Renewable energy sources 3. Improvement in energy efficiency 4. Security of energy supply 5. Energy market 6. Agriculture, shipping, tourism (new theme) 7. Research, innovation and competitiveness) <p>The NECP addresses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An integrated model for sustainable and viable growth in all economic sectors • Combined energy sector development and environmental protection through bold measures for addressing climate change • Choosing energy policies with the most cost-benefit ratio for energy transition • Waste management and utilisation by the use of state-of-the-art circular economy technologies • Transforming Greece into an energy hub with a strong contribution to the EU's energy security and security of supply • Ensuring the strategic diversification of energy imports, while at the same time modernising and developing energy infrastructures and putting an end to the energy isolation of the islands • Setting up attractive investment environment to support energy transition, focusing on innovation and new technologies • Ensuring the maximum possible use of community resources and mechanisms • Ensuring openness and innovation in order to achieve growth that will create new jobs
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p><u>Barriers-delays:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The technical measures described in the NECP are not accompanied by a mobilization of investment costs. • Limited mobilization of private funds.
References	<p>Greek NECP (2019), url-EN: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-03/el_final_necp_main_en_0.pdf</p>

No. of Element	8
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Long-term strategy for the renovation of the public and private building stock and its transformation into high energy efficiency low carbon building stock by 2050 (approval by Ministerial Decision)

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Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	<p>The Law presents the Strategy for the implementation of L.4342/2015 regarding the energy renovation of buildings (Article 4 of 2012/27/EU).</p> <p>It includes policy measures for triggering investments towards the energy upgrading of the national building stock; estimations and projections of buildings' energy retrofiting rates towards 2030; policy recommendations to comply with the 3% renovation rates of buildings owned or occupied by the central government.</p>
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p><u>Progress:</u></p> <p>Some of the policy measures included in the strategy have been implemented and respective incentives / funding programmes launched.</p>
References	<p>Ministerial decision-Approval of the “Long-term strategy for the renovation of the public and private building stock and its transformation into high energy efficiency low carbon building stock by 2050”, Ministry of Environment and Energy, url-GR: https://ypen.gov.gr/energeia/energeiaki-exoikonomisi/ktiria/ltrs/</p>

No. of Element	9
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	16 Sustainable Energy (and Climate) Action Plans (SEAPs / SECAPs) of Municipalities in the Region of Crete, in the framework of the Covenant of Mayors initiative
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	Local (Municipal)
Description / key aspects	<p>The EU Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy is the world's largest movement for local climate and energy actions. It brings together thousands of local governments voluntarily committed to implementing EU climate and energy objectives.</p> <p>In order to translate their political commitment into practical measures and projects, Covenant signatories (Mayors from all over Europe) commit to submitting, within two years following the date of the local council decision, a Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP) outlining the key actions they plan to undertake.</p>

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	<p>The commitments for Covenant signatories are linked to the EU's climate and energy policy framework: the 2020 climate and energy package for signatories who have joined between 2008 and 2015 and the 2030 climate and energy framework as well as the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change for signatories joining after 2015.</p> <p>Covenant signatories commit to adopting an integrated approach to climate change mitigation and adaptation. They are required to develop, within the first two years of adhesion, a Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan with the aims of cutting CO₂ emissions by at least 40% by 2030 and increasing resilience to climate change.</p>
<p>Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)</p>	<p><u>Progress:</u></p> <p>18 Municipalities of the Region of Crete are signatories of the Covenant of Mayors Community while 16 Municipalities have submitted a Sustainable Energy Action Plan.</p> <p><u>Barriers-delays:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of monitoring reports (only 4 of the 16 Municipalities submitted monitoring/progress reports) • Lack of data regarding the energy consumption and climate and energy indicators • There is not direct involvement of the technical staff of the municipality (external contractor typically prepares SEAP)
<p>References</p>	<p>16 SEAPs / SECAPs of Municipalities in Crete:</p> <p>Apokoronou (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>Kandanou-Selinou (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>Platanias (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>Chania (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>Anogia (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>Dimos Mylopotamou (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>Rethymno (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>Viannos (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>Heraklion (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>Malevizi (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>Minoa Pediadas (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>Festos (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>Hersonisos (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>Aghios Nikolaos (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>IERAPETRA (covenantofmayors.eu)</p> <p>Sitia (covenantofmayors.eu)</p>

No. of Element	10
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Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.).	Regional Plan for the Adaptation to Climate Change of the Region of Crete
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	Regional
Description / key aspects	<p>Developing a climate change adaptation strategy is a National and Regional obligation arising from the Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC, 1992), the Paris Agreement and the EU commitments.</p> <p>The Region of Crete has recently completed the Study of the "Regional Plan for Climate Change Adaptation of the Region of Crete" which is the strategy to address the threat of climate change, with the main goal of reducing the vulnerability of the Region resulting from climate change and its shielding against it.</p> <p>The elaboration, as well as the specifications and the specific content of the Regional Plan for the Adaptation to Climate Change (RPACC) are specified by the Ministerial Decision no. 11258/2017 (Government Gazette 873 /B/ 16-03-2017). The project has been financed by the Operational Program of Crete, priority axis 2 "Sustainable Development by upgrading the environment and addressing the effects of climate change in Crete.</p> <p>The "Regional Plan for Climate Change Adaptation" elaborates the changes that will occur in the coming decades in the Region by assessing 14 key areas affected by the effects of climate change and the geographical areas that should be given priority were identified. The study also identifies and prioritizes the necessary measures and actions for adaptation to climate change for the next 5 to 15 years, their timeline and costs.</p> <p>The "Regional Plan for Climate Change Adaptation" is expected to be a guide for the Region and will allow municipalities and other competent bodies to prepare and mature all projects related to adaptation to climate change, for their successful integration in the new programming period for the NSRF (2021 - 2027).</p>
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	Progress: Public consultation was officially closed in February 2022 and the document was finally proof-read and approved by the Regional Council.
References	Regional Plan for Climate Change Adaptation: https://www.safecrete.gr/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/PESPKA_Crete_upd_1221-%CF%84%CE%B5%CE%BB%CE%B5%CF%85%CF%84%CE%B1%CE%AF%CE%B1-%

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	https://www.safecrete.gr
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No. of Element	11
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.).	Municipal Sustainable Mobility Action Plans and Sustainable Micro-mobility Action Plans
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	Regional
Description / key aspects	<p>The Law 4784/2021 about Sustainable Mobility Action Plans and the Micro-mobility was one of the key enforcement measures to promote the development of SMAPs in Crete. Among others, this law enforces and includes measures in the national Road Traffic Code for e-scooters, roller skates and skate boards, Self-balancing vehicles (such as Segway) and electric vehicles that do not fall into any of the above categories.</p> <p>So far the 6 largest Cretan municipalities (Heraklion, Rethymno, Chania, Malevizi, Agios Nikolaos, Ierapetra) are developing their Sustainable Mobility Action Plans considering among others the reduction of CO₂ emissions from all the means of public transportation, while more than 10 have applied in the recent Open call of the Green Fund for the development of a strategic plan for Micro-mobility.</p> <p>The National observatory of Sustainable Mobility Action Plans is presented in the following link: https://www.svak.gr/</p>
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	Sustainable Mobility Action Plans and the Micro-mobility.
References	<p>6 Sustainable Mobility Action Plans of Cretan Municipalities:</p> <p>Sustainable Mobility Action Plan of Heraklion</p> <p>Sustainable Mobility Action Plan of Rethymno</p> <p>Sustainable Mobility Action Plan of Chania</p> <p>Sustainable Mobility Action Plan of Agios Nikolaos</p> <p>Sustainable Mobility Action Plan of Malevizi</p>

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	Sustainable Mobility Action Plan of Irapetra
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5.1.2 Spain / Region of Catalonia / Province of Girona

No. of Element	1
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Royal Decree 235/2013, on 5th April, approving the basic procedure for the certification of the energy performance of buildings - Transposition of the recast EPBD directive 2010/31/EU into the Spanish legislation
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	It establishes the obligation to make available to building purchasers or users an energy performance certificate which should include objective information on the energy performance of a building and reference values, such as minimum energy performance requirements, in order to enable owners or tenants of the building or a building unit to compare and assess its energy performance.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	Repealed on June 3 rd 2021
References	RD235/2013 url-ES: https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2013/04/05/235/con

No. of Element	2
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Royal Decree 56/2016, on 12th February, on energy efficiency, as regards energy audits, accreditation of energy service providers and auditors, and promotion of the efficiency of energy supply - Transposition of the EED directive 2012/27/EU into the Spanish legislation
Applicability level	National

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(national, regional, local)	
Description / key aspects	<p>RD 56/2016 has two main objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To drive and promote a set of actions to be carried out within the energy consumption processes that contribute to the saving and efficiency of the primary energy consumed in Spain, as well as to optimise the energy demand of the facilities, equipment or energy consuming systems. To have a sufficient number of competent and reliable professionals registered in the List of Energy Service Providers in order to ensure the effective and timely implementation of the aforementioned Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<u>Delay:</u> The transposition of 2012/27/EU came late after several reprimands.
References	RD 56/2016 url-ES: https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2016/02/12/56/con

No. of Element	3
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Royal Decree 732/2019, on 20th December, amending the Spanish Technical Building Code (Código Técnico de la Edificación) - Transposition of directive 2018/844/EU into the Spanish legislation (amending 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings and 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency)
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	<p>The Law updated the Technical Building Code (CTE) in several aspects. The main modifications are given in the Basic Document (DB) on Energy Saving (HE) which is further divided into 6 basic requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> HE 0: Energy consumption constraints HE 1: Energy demand control conditions HE 2: Thermal system conditions HE 3: Lighting system conditions HE 4: Minimum contribution of renewable energy to cover domestic hot water demand. HE 5: Minimum power generation
Implementation status	

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(progress; barriers; delays)	
References	RD 732/2019 url-ES: https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2019/12/20/732

No. of Element	4
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Royal Decree 244/2019, on 5th April, on self-consumption of electric energy
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	<p>The law provide new incentives for Spanish prosumers by establishing compensation mechanisms and simplifying administrative procedures. The modifications affected the definition of self-consumption (to include collective self-consumption) and reduced the forms of self-consumption to two (self-consumption with or without surplus). It also simplified the registration of the installations and eliminated the need to get access and connexion permits for some production installations (without surplus). Two different legal standards for self-consumers, according to the installed capacity were defined:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Installations between 15 and 100 kW, which only need to process a connection point with a distribution system operator (DSO) company ▪ Installations higher than 100 kW which are not considered as prosumers. <p>In general, the new regulation improved the situation of PV prosumers. On the one hand, it simplified the technical and administrative requirements. On the other hand, it improved the economic viability of the PV systems by removing the backup charge and recognizing the right of prosumers to sell the surplus electricity to the grid. In-deed, the regulation explicitly mentions three guiding principles (RD-L 15/2018p. 97434):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Right to self-consume electrical energy without charges 2. Right to shared self-consumption by one or several consumers 3. Principle of technical and administrative simplification, especially for low power installations.

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Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	In the case of collective schemes, the new DL specified that compensation for surplus energy includes a distribution of the savings among neighbours. Although energy communities are not specifically mentioned, technical and economic aspects relevant for collective prosumers are regulated under RD 244/2019. Jointly acting self-consumers are considered “neighbour communities” formed by those within one apartment block. According to this law, the self-consumer must beat a maximum distance of 500 m from the installation.
References	RD 244/2019 url-ES: https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2019/04/05/244

No. of Element	5
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Royal Decree-law 23/2020, on 23 rd June, adopting energy and other measures for economic recovery
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	One of the objectives for Energy Transition of Spain is to achieve an electricity system based 100 % on Renewable Energies by 2050. The Royal Decree-Law is divided into four blocks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) the first block includes the regulation of access and connection and regulates a new auction mechanism to provide renewables with a predictable and stable framework; ii) ii) the second block focuses on the promotion of new business models that will be key in the coming years, such as demand aggregation, storage and hybridisation; iii) the third block addresses the promotion of energy efficiency by making the National Energy Efficiency Fund more flexible; iv) the fourth block establishes a series of sectoral measures to boost economic activity and employment in response to the COVID-19 crisis.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	The royal decree removes barriers to the massive deployment of renewable sources, defines new business models and promotes energy efficiency, among other issues.
References	RD 23/2020 url-ES: https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rdl/2020/06/23/23/con

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No. of Element	6
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Law 16/2017, on 1 st August, of climate change
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	Regional
Description / key aspects	<p>The Catalan Government approved the Climate Change Law on July 2017 based on a National Agreement for energy transition, for which regarding to the improvement of governance in the field of energy the main challenges faced are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Place energy policy at a higher level in decision-making processes • Build a shared vision as regards the energy challenges, establishing clear and ambitious medium-term targets. • Increase citizens' knowledge and understanding of energy and their awareness of its economic and environmental costs • Agreeing on the path towards energy transition in cooperation with social stakeholders • Overcoming resistance to change within the traditional power structures • Encouraging citizen participation in the decision-making process as regards energy infrastructure and facilities.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	The law aims to ensure that Catalonia reduces greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and promotes the transition to a low-carbon economy.
References	<p>L. 16/2017 url-CAT: https://cido.diba.cat/legislacio/7200647/llei-162017-de-l1-dagost-del-canvi-climatic-departament-de-la-presidencia</p>

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5.1.3 Czech Republic / Zlín Region

No. of Element	1
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Decree No. 264/2020 Coll., on the energy performance of buildings - Transposition of the recast EPBD directives 2010/31/EU, 2012/27/EU and 2018/844/EU into the Czech legislation
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	<p>The Ministry of Industry and Trade has prepared Decree No. 264/2020 Coll., On the energy performance of buildings), which will replace Decree No. 78/2013 Coll. , on the energy performance of buildings, as amended.</p> <p>In preparing this decree, the Ministry responded to the need to implement the new Directive (EU) 2018/844 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 amending Directive 2010/31 / EU on the energy performance of buildings and Directive 2012/27 / EU on energy efficiency. This directive newly regulates, for example, the calculation of energy demand, it places greater emphasis on achieving a quality indoor environment in buildings while reducing energy demand.</p> <p>Decree 264/2020 Coll., further regulates the requirements for so-called buildings with nearly zero energy consumption (NZEBs). The former setting of NZEBs parameters didn't reflect the achieved technological development and deviated significantly from the NZEBs parameters set out in Commission Recommendation (EU) 2016/1318 on guidelines for the promotion of NZEBs and best practices to ensure that by 2020 all new buildings are with almost zero energy consumption.</p>
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	Decree No. 264/2020 Coll. was published in the Collection of Laws on 5 June 2020 and entered into force on 1 September 2020, thus repealing the current decree in force.

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	Some further modifications were proposed on the basis of practical experience with the application of the current wording of the current decree. The aim of these adjustments was to increase the quality and credibility of the building's energy performance certificate, comparability of building energy performance results, updates due to technical development, extension of energy saving measures, changes in the Czech energy mix and bringing the building energy performance certificate closer to the general public.
References	<p>Ministry of Industry and Trade info on the Decree No. 264/2020 Coll:</p> <p>Vyhláška č. 264/2020 Sb., o energetické náročnosti budov MPO</p> <p>Decree No. 264/2020 Coll available on the Ministry of Interior website (PDF link).</p> <p>https://aplikace.mvcr.cz/sbirka-zakonu/ViewFile.aspx?type=c&id=38880</p>

No. of Element	2
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	<p>Legislation on Energy Communities in the Czech Republic (in development, likely to be incorporated into the Law No. 458/2000 Coll., Energy Act)</p> <p>The objective is to assist local actors and citizens willing to set up a Citizens Energy Community (as defined in the EU Electricity Market Directive 2019/944) or a Renewable Energy Community (as defined in the EU Renewable Energy Directive 2018/2001)</p>
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	The Energy Act has to deal with the new reality of the energy market characterized by a large number of active entities that carry out various activities (generation, consumption, accumulation, or aggregation of energy). The updated Energy Act should be submitted to the government in the course of 2022. By-laws then lay down market rules (eg sharing).
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	The main barrier to the development of energy communities in the Czech Republic is mainly non-existent implementing legislation and the related definition of permissible legal forms of the energy community. There are also no rules for participating in and sharing electricity (as a distinction from trading it). A major obstacle to development is also the obligation to have an energy trading license if it is not just a common supply point or a local distribution system. The adjustment of the tariff structure is then a prerequisite for the willingness of citizens to participate in community energy at all.

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	Energy communities will be supported through both new and existing financial instruments at the national level, such as the Modernization Fund, the Operational Program Environment or the New Green Savings Program.
References	Frank Bold Company link (energy communities legislation development assisting company): Komunitní energetika v Česku stojí na startovní čáře. Jak vypadá legislativa a financování? Frank Bold

No. of Element	3
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	Government Resolution No. 685 on the introduction of the Rules for the Support of Low-Emission Vehicles through Public Procurement and Public Passenger Transport Services - transposition of directive 2019/1161/EU into the Czech legislation.
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	<p>The scope of the Rules is regulated in Article 2, according to which the Rules apply to contracts concluded before 31 December 2025, specifically to contracts for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - public contracts for the purchase, leasing or rental of passenger and light commercial vehicles (categories M1, M2 and N1), lorries (categories N2 and N3) or buses (categories M3 / I and M3 / A), but with a number of exceptions, eg for agricultural or forestry vehicles (more details in Article 2, paragraph 3 of the Rules), - above-limit public service contracts pursuant to Annex No. 1 to the Rules (eg public road transport services), which the contracting authority was obliged to award in a procurement procedure under the Public Procurement Act, with the exception of the concession procedure, if these services will be provided by a vehicle described in the previous point; - public passenger transport services under the Public Passenger Transport Services Act for which the average annual value or number of kilometres per year exceeds the limit values [4], if these services are provided by means of one of the vehicles described above. <p>For the purposes of the Rules, a low-emission vehicle means a vehicle which, in the case of passenger cars and light road vehicles, does not exceed the set emission limits, resp. which uses alternative fuels in the case of lorries and buses. Alternative fuel means a fuel or energy source that serves, at least in part, to replace fossil oil resources in the supply of energy for transport and that has the potential to contribute to its decarbonisation and</p>

	<p>increase the environmental performance of the transport sector; the alternative fuel is mainly biofuel or other fuel from renewable sources, synthetic and paraffinic fuel, compressed natural gas including biomethane, liquefied natural gas including biomethane, liquefied petroleum gas, electricity and hydrogen. A low-emission vehicle also means a trolleybus.</p> <p>According to the Rules, the minimum shares of low-emission vehicles that must be achieved in the first monitoring period from the effectiveness of the Rules to 31 December 2025 are as follows:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="555 645 1375 925"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Min. share of low-emission vehicles by the end of 2025</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Passenger and light commercial vehicles (categories M1, M2 and N1)</td> <td>29,7 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Trucks (categories N2 and N3)</td> <td>9 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Buses (categories M3 / I and M3 / A)</td> <td>41 %</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Min. share of low-emission vehicles by the end of 2025	Passenger and light commercial vehicles (categories M1, M2 and N1)	29,7 %	Trucks (categories N2 and N3)	9 %	Buses (categories M3 / I and M3 / A)	41 %
	Min. share of low-emission vehicles by the end of 2025								
Passenger and light commercial vehicles (categories M1, M2 and N1)	29,7 %								
Trucks (categories N2 and N3)	9 %								
Buses (categories M3 / I and M3 / A)	41 %								
<p>Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)</p>	<p>In January 2021, the Government submitted to the Chamber of Deputies of the Parliament of the Czech Republic bill on the support of low-emission vehicles in public procurement and public passenger transport services (registered as Chamber Press No. 1121) but it did not even survive the discussion in the first reading before parliamentary elections to the Chamber of Deputies. With regard to the set end of the transposition period of the Directive, the government (on the proposal of the Ministry of Regional Development and the Ministry of Transport) proceeded to a partial, resp. temporary transposition, when on 26 July 2021 it approved Government Resolution No. 685 on the introduction of the Rules for the Support of Low-Emission Vehicles through the Procurement of Public Contracts and Public Passenger Transport Services</p> <p>The resolution required members of the government and heads of other central state administration bodies to follow the Rules, which form an annex to the cited resolution, in the organizations under their control. Other public contracting authorities and sectoral contracting authorities pursuant to § 4 para. b), d) and e) and paragraph 3 of Act No. 134/2016 Coll., on the award of public contracts, as amended (Public Procurement Act)</p> <p>The rules are effective from 2 August 2021 until the entry into force and effect of the regulation at the level of the law, while the obligations contained therein apply to contracts that were concluded on the basis of tenders or tenders launched after 2 August 2021 (including direct assignment, which the customer started negotiating after this date).</p> <p>Although the solution is temporary, it mitigates the risk of not meeting the EU targets. At the meeting of the Government on 6 December 2021, the Minister for Regional Development re-submitted a bill on the support of low-emission vehicles in the award of public contracts and public passenger transport services (material no. 1392/21), as in the new term of the Chamber of</p>								

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	Deputies in principle, proposals that were not discussed and decided in the last parliamentary term cannot be discussed. The bill will therefore be resubmitted to the newly established Chamber of Deputies in the near future; however, the Rules will be effective throughout the legislative process until the draft law enters into force.
References	Government Resolution No. 685 on the introduction of the Rules for the Support of Low-Emission Vehicles through Public Procurement and Public Passenger Transport Services IHOAC5DBT6TM (odok.cz) Pravidla podpory nízkoemisních vozidel prostředn epravo.cz

No. of Element	4
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	The implementation of EU Directive 2018/2002 (amending Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency) is carried out in 3 different laws: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Amendment to Act No. 406/2000 Coll., Energy Management Act - new information obligations in § 6 of Decree No. 269/2015 Coll. on the allocation of costs for heating and joint preparation of hot water for the house - Draft amendment to Act No. 67/2013 Coll., which regulates certain issues related to the provision of services associated with the use of apartments and non-residential premises in a house with apartments
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	The amendment to Act No. 406/2000 Coll., The Energy Management Act with effect from 1 January 2022, introduces: All meters and devices registering the supply of heat or cold from the heat supply system or with central heating or cooling or joint hot water preparation, installed after 1.1.2022 must be equipped with remotely readable specified meters and remotely readable devices to the extent and in the manner specified by implementing legislation. All existing meters and devices registering the supply of thermal energy must be replaced by remotely readable by 1 January 2027. Among the new information obligations in § 6 of Decree No. 269/2015 Coll. belong:

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	<p>a) information on the energy mix used and the related annual greenhouse gas emissions per unit of account for the last calendar year for which it is available, if thermal energy from district heating systems has been supplied to the service provider</p> <p>b) information on energy demand and the share of energy from renewable sources in the heat supply system, if the heat supplier has provided this information in the bill pursuant to the legal regulation governing the bill of supplies and related services in the energy sectors</p> <p>c) a description of individual taxes, fees and other similar pecuniary benefits, which are included in the price of thermal energy supplied by service providers from district heating systems and which are directly related to the amount of supplied thermal energy, if this description was provided by the thermal energy supplier in the bill supplies and related services in the energy sectors, etc.</p> <p>Draft amendment to Act No. 67/2013 Coll. With supposed effect from 01/01/2023:</p> <p>If remotely readable meters or devices for distributing heating costs and co-hot water consumption are installed, the service provider delivers information to the service recipient about its detected (recalculated) heat and co-hot water consumption.</p> <p>Unless the service provider agrees otherwise with a two-thirds majority of the tenants in the house, or the cooperative or community decides otherwise, information on the identified heat consumption and co-prepared hot water for the calendar month is provided and the service provider delivers it to the recipient by the end of the following calendar month.</p> <p>The obligation shall be deemed to be fulfilled if the service provider makes available to the recipient of the services information on his consumption in a manner enabling remote access and notifies the recipient of the services of this release within the same time limit for providing the information.</p>
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p>The amendment to Act No. 406/2000 Coll., The Energy Management Act with effect from 1 January 2022</p> <p>Decree No. 269/2015 Coll. on the allocation of costs for heating and joint preparation of hot water for the house with effect from 2.11.2021</p> <p>The amendment to Act No. 67/2013 Coll., The Services Act, is expected to take effect on 1 January 2023</p>
References	<p>Implementace směrnice EU 2018/2002, která zavádí povinnost dálkového odečtu tepla a teplé vody a měsíční informace o spotřebě do české legislativy již od 1.1.2022 (webdomu.cz)</p>

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Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)	The Czech Republic 's national energy and climate plan The Czech Republic's national plan in the field of energy and climate was prepared on the basis of the requirements of Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 of the European Parliament and of the European Council on the administration of the Energy Union and climate action.
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	National
Description / key aspects	<p>The obligation to prepare a National Energy and Climate Plan follows from Article 3 of the EU Regulation on Energy and Climate Action, which entered into force on 24 December 2018. The document was prepared in close cooperation with other ministries and other relevant bodies. On 13 January 2020, the document was approved by the Government of the Czech Republic and authorized by the Ministry of Industry and Trade to formally forward the document to representatives of the European Commission. The document was forwarded to the European Commission immediately after this decision.</p> <p>The document contains objectives and main policies in all five dimensions of the so-called Energy Union. Through this document, Member States have, inter alia, the obligation to inform the European Commission of the national contribution to the agreed European targets for greenhouse gas emissions, renewable energy sources, energy efficiency and interconnection of the electricity and transmission systems, respectively.</p>
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p>The plan envisages an increase in the share of renewables in total energy consumption by 2030 to 22%. In addition to electricity, the indicator also includes renewable energy in transport, heating and cooling.</p> <p>The Czech Republic's National Plan for Energy and Climate was approved by the Government of the Czech Republic and submitted to the representatives of the European Commission</p>
References	<p>The Czech Republic's national energy and climate plan: https://www.mpo.cz/assets/cz/energetika/strategicke-a-koncepcni-dokumenty/2020/1/Vnitrostani-plan-CR-v-oblasti-energetiky-a-klimatu_final.docx Vnitrostátní plán České republiky v oblasti energetiky a klimatu MPO</p>

No. of Element	6
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<p>Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.)</p>	<p>The Energy Action Plan and the Energy Efficiency Financing Plan of the Zlín Region 2020 - 2024</p>
<p>Applicability level (national, regional, local)</p>	<p>Regional</p>
<p>Description / key aspects</p>	<p>The Energy Action Plan and the Energy Efficiency Financing Plan of the Zlín Region is a programming document based on the approved documents of the Zlín Region for the area of energy and the environment, in particular air protection. It is based on 5 pillars of the Regional Energy Strategy.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. A balanced mix of resources - based on their broad portfolio, efficient use of all available domestic energy resources and maintaining the ES's surplus power balance with ample reserves. II. Increasing energy efficiency and achieving energy savings in the economy and in households. III. Development of the Czech Republic's network infrastructure in the context of Central European countries, strengthening international cooperation and integration of electricity and gas markets in the region IV. Support for research, development and innovation ensuring the competitiveness of Czech energy and support for education V. Increasing of energy safety and resilience of the Czech Republic and strengthening the ability to secure the necessary energy supplies in the occasion of failures cumulation, multiple attacks against critical infrastructure and in cases of prolonged fuel supply crises. <p>The EE Action Plan of the Zlín Region outlines 5 priorities that are based on the Regional Energy Strategy:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Support for efficient use of energy in buildings owned by the Zlín Region 2. Support for efficient use of energy in the region 3. Promoting the use of renewables, secondary and prospective energy sources 4. Increasing security and reliability of energy supply 5. Measures to support the implementation of the Action Plan
<p>Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)</p>	<p>The plan was approved by the advisory board as well as Assembly of the Zlín Region in December 2019 and currently is being implemented.</p>

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References	<p>The Energy Action Plan_Zlín_Region_ET</p>
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No. of Element	7
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.).	Regional Action Plan for the Zlín Region
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	Regional
Description / key aspects	<p>The elaboration of the action plan for the Zlín Region was based on a participatory approach with the involvement of representatives of the Zlín Region, towns and municipalities of the Zlín Region and other local and regional important and relevant stakeholders. The key stakeholders at the national level were, for example, members of the OP Environment Monitoring Committee from the National Network of Local Action Groups or from the State Environmental Fund administering OP Environment. All stakeholders are directly or indirectly involved in building renovation and energy-efficient building activities, the creation and renovation of district heating and other urban renewal actions in the regions.</p> <p>The aim of the project is to implement a regional action plan with the aim of improving the national strategic instrument - the Operational Program Environment. The specific area on which the project focuses and for which it aims to optimize the use of public funds is listed in the OPE 2014-2020 program under priority 5.1 - Decrease the energy demand of public buildings and increase the use of renewable energy sources. The aim of the measure is buildings with a high potential for cost-effective solutions.</p>
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p>The Regional Action Plan for the Zlín Region is currently in its implementation phase, realising the main covering action of it, which is Promoting of new projects supporting the energy efficiency in public buildings and thus striving to achieve the three main goals foreseen:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of final energy consumption in public buildings - Increasing the number of approved projects - Adapt existing tools to regional and local conditions
References	Link to the RAP of the Zlín Region:

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	Regional Action Plan for the Zlín Region - Energetická agentura Zlínského kraje, o.p.s. (eazk.cz)
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5.2 Governance status in existing EU networks and initiatives

The following tables present a review of the governance status in relation to **energy transition**, in current **EU-wide networks and initiatives** related to the project objectives, including:

- **Governance structures / figures** introduced by these networks, for coordinating and monitoring energy transition plans and actions. These may be either within the networks themselves (e.g. secretariat, council, committee etc.) or within public authorities (e.g. local council, designated personnel etc.);
- **Tools / methodologies / digital platforms** introduced by these networks for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities, including the type and format of data required to be collected.

The main objectives of the provided elements are described as well as the implementation status e.g. progress, expected or achieved impacts and possible barriers.

No. of Network/ initiative	1
Network name	Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy - Europe
Network website	https://www.covenantofmayors.eu/ From June 2021 the website will move to https://eumayors.eu/
Number of Members	10,948 Signatories, 233 Coordinators, 241 Supporters
Countries coverage	54 countries (Note: Support is only provided for EU + EFTA + Balkans + Turkey + UK. Other countries can join but do not get support by CoM)
Description of network	<p>Launched in 2008, the CoM has grown to be the largest movement for local climate and energy actions, bringing together thousands of local governments voluntarily committed to implementing EU climate and energy objectives. Commitment of signatories to achieve 40% CO₂ reduction in their territories by 2030 and common approach for the mitigation and adaptation to climate change. Shared vision for decarbonization by 2050.</p> <p>CoM signatories (municipalities from all over the EU and beyond) commit to submitting, within two years following the date of their adherence to the CoM, a Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP) outlining the key actions they plan to undertake.</p>

<p>Introduced governance structure / figure for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)</p>	<p>CoM - Europe is based on a multi-governance approach, with the following structure:</p> <p>Signatories: Local authorities e.g. Municipalities (whatever their size and stage of implementation of their energy and climate policies). Local authorities can join groups for the development of joint action plans.</p> <p>Coordinators: Public authorities that provide strategic guidance and technical support to CoM Europe signatories for developing, implementing and monitoring their local action plans.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Territorial coordinators: decentralized authorities such as Regions, provinces or grouping of local authorities. • National coordinators: national public bodies such as ministries or national energy agencies. <p>Supporters: Associations of local and regional authorities, thematic local and regional agencies and organisations of the civil society with the capacity to promote the Covenant of Mayors Europe and to mobilise and support their members and/or local authorities to attain the CoM Europe objectives.</p> <p>The CoM - Europe Office is responsible for the overall coordination and implementation of the CoM Europe initiative. It is managed by a consortium of European networks and associations of local/regional entities (Energy Cities, CEMR, Climate Alliance, Eurocities, FEDARENE, ICLEI Europe) and of 1 ICT company Akaryon.</p> <p>The European Commission (DG ENER and DG CLIMA) and the Joint Research Centre also form part of the Covenant Community: the first committing to mobilise funds for the Covenant members; the JRC providing technical support for the development of local action plans.</p>
<p>Introduced tool / methodology / digital platform for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities</p>	<p><u>Tool:</u></p> <p>Structure for Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP) and related guidance</p> <p>Local authorities joining the CoM - Europe initiative commit to submitting an action plan within <u>two years</u> after formally signing up to the initiative. This action plan is a key implementation tool for the Covenant signatories. It defines mitigation target(s), adaptation goal(s) and energy poverty goals and is based on a Baseline Emission Inventory, a Risk & Vulnerability Assessment and an Energy Poverty Assessment, which provide an analysis of the current situation at a given moment. They serve as a basis for defining a comprehensive set of actions that signatories plan to undertake to reach their targets.</p> <p>The minimum reporting requirements refer to the mandatory data from the action plan and monitoring reports that signatories need to provide through the MyCovenant platform or the Unified Reporting System (see description of GCoM below).</p>

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	<p>An offline excel version of the MyCovenant reporting template is provided in the CoM - Europe website (see ‘References’), that can be used by signatories as a working document during the preparation of their reporting.</p> <p><u>Digital platform for reporting/monitoring:</u></p> <p>MyCovenant is one of the 2 reporting platforms recognised by the European Commission and the Covenant of Mayors - Europe. MyCovenant is directly managed by the Covenant of Mayors - Europe Office. Once signed in, Signatories, Coordinators and Supporters are able to update their contact information and access both the “reporting corner” and the “capacity-sharing corner”.</p> <p>Its Reporting Corner includes the templates to report and monitor the data of their local action plans. Reported data allows signatories to demonstrate the concrete impact of their actions and their climate ambitions. The Covenant - Europe template allows signatories to collect and analyse data in a structured and systematic manner, and serves as a basis for good climate and energy management and for tracking progress in implementation.</p>
<p>Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)</p>	<p>Since its initial launch in 2008, CoM - Europe has grown to be the largest movement for local climate and energy actions, bringing together thousands of local governments voluntarily committed to implementing EU climate and energy objectives.</p> <p>The initiative key success factors are considered to be the introduced bottom-up approach to energy and climate actions, the multi-level cooperation model and its context-driven framework for action. The initiative now gathers 10,000+ local and regional authorities across 54 countries.</p>
<p>References</p>	<p>What is the CoM - Europe Office? https://eumayors.eu/images/FAQs-2021.pdf</p> <p>CoM - Europe reporting guidelines: https://eumayors.eu/index.php?option=com_attachments&task=download&id=857</p> <p>Offline simplified SECAP excel template: https://www.covenantofmayors.eu/component/attachments/?task=download&id=816</p> <p>Access to MyCovenant (registration needed): https://mycovenant.eumayors.eu/site/landing</p>

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No. of Network/ initiative	2
Network name	Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy
Network website	https://www.globalcovenantofmayors.org/
<p>GLOBAL COVENANT of MAYORS for CLIMATE & ENERGY</p>	
Number of Members	11,754 cities
Countries coverage	6 continents - 142 countries
Description of network	<p>The Global CoM for Climate & Energy (GCoM) is the largest global alliance for city climate leadership, build upon the commitment of over 11,500 cities and local governments sharing a long-term vision for combatting climate change. GCoM was created in 2017, formally bringing together the EU Covenant of Mayors (launched in 2008) and the Compact of Mayors (launched in 2014) - the world's two primary initiatives of cities and local governments - to advance city-level climate action and demonstrate global impact.</p> <p>GCoM serves cities and local governments by mobilizing and supporting ambitious, measurable and planned climate and energy action in their communities.</p> <p>Committed cities work towards compliance with the GCoM framework and as part of their commitments, signatories: (1) develop a greenhouse gas emissions inventory and report their results; (2) assess climate risks and vulnerabilities; (3) define climate change mitigation targets; (4) develop integrated climate action plans to meet their stated targets and goals; (5) implement planned measures to reach targets and goals; (6) monitor, measure and report progress on a regular basis, to share their results and improve their ambition implementation over time.</p>
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	The GCoM global governance structure is as follows:

Global CoM Board: The Board provides the strategic direction for the initiative. Ten mayors and local officials serve on the Board, acting as representatives of core partner networks and providing regionally specific perspectives.

Strategic Advisory Committee (SAC) to the Board: It is comprised of global, regional and national city networks, Regional/National Covenants, Ex-Officio Board Members and representatives from the European Commission and the European Committee of the Regions. It helps set the strategic direction for ultimate approval by the Board.

SAC Members:

Committed cities working towards compliance with the GCoM framework benefit from direct support from GCoM partners in the form of technical assistance, training, advisory support and analysis and peer-to-peer learning programs.

- *European Networks & Partners:* Energy Cities, CEMR, Climate Alliance, Eurocities, FEDARENE, ICLEI Europe, European Commission, European Committee of the Regions

- *Global City Networks & Partners:* C40 Cities, United Cities and Local Governments (UCLG), ICLEI, CDP, UN Habitat, United Nations Climate Change

- *Regional Networks & Partners:* Caribbean Association of Local Government Authorities (CALGA), Federation of Canadian Municipalities (FCM), ICLEI Japan, ICLEI South Korea, ICLEI Oceania, ICLEI SAMS Latin America, ICLEI South Asia, UCLG Middle East and West Asia, UCLG Africa, UCLG South East Asia, Urban Sustainability Directors Network (USDN) United States.

The Funders Group: It is comprised of the main funders of the GCoM alliance to set funding priorities and ensure coordination across funding sources.

The Global Secretariat: Based in Brussels, it serves as an organising platform for the Global CoM work and provides support

	<p>to the National/Regional Covenants established across the globe. Support is provided through five Technical Working Groups providing recommendations and guidance for implementation of the GCoM:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Global and Regional Coherence 2) Data Management, Monitoring and Reporting 3) Finance 4) Communications 5) Research and Innovation <p>Regional / National Covenants: They serve as local chapters of the global GCoM. Each engages city, sub-national and national governments, community alliances and parallel initiatives to encourage and support climate action from the ground up. They encourage stakeholders at the local, national and regional levels to accelerate climate action. They oversee the development of technical assistance plans for cities, ensuring a Common Reporting Framework is implemented.</p> <p>Regional / National Secretariats: All Regional / National Covenants are supported by operation teams structured as formal or informal Secretariats. They are responsible for coordination and facilitate joint planning and strategy for the region. They also provide capacity building activities and liaise with the GCoM Secretariat.</p> <p>Tailored governance structures: They have been/are being established through each Regional/National Covenant, as coordination and decision-making mechanisms among stakeholders (e.g. coordination group, advisory committee, steering group/committee, etc.) which recognise regional specificities and aim at strengthening information sharing, strategic steering and cooperation in local climate action. These mechanisms are key to ensure the collaborative governance of the Covenants and to encourage the identification and implementation of joint approaches for all the GCoM partners in a given region/country.</p>
<p>Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities</p>	<p><u>Digital platform for reporting/monitoring:</u></p> <p>Signatory cities must follow the GCoM’s Common Reporting Framework, the global framework for reporting city greenhouse gas inventories, risk and vulnerability assessments and climate action plans. GCoM developed this Common Reporting Framework in consultation with partners and cities and local governments around the world. This framework includes a set of global recommendations to ensure robust climate action planning, implementation and monitoring, and streamline measurement and reporting procedures.</p> <p>The Global CoM recognizes two official platforms for reporting on climate and energy measures: the MyCovenant Platform (already described in Element 1 above) and the CDP-ICLEI Unified Reporting System, both aligning to the Global CoM Common Reporting Framework. While both reporting systems are fully adapted for European signatory cities to report on their climate</p>

	<p>action commitments, there are several differences between these platforms.</p> <p>Cities’ responses submitted through either of the platforms are assessed to determine compliance with the GCoM requirements, and where compliance is achieved, badges are awarded and reflected on the GCoM website.</p> <p>CDP-ICLEI Unified Reporting System</p> <p>In April 2019, CDP and ICLEI partnered to present one unified platform for city climate reporting. By streamlining ICLEI’s carbon Climate Registry (cCR) and CDP’s reporting platform into an unique reporting system, both organizations aimed to ensure simplicity and standardisation for reporting cities and to provide a clearer picture of the scope and impact of subnational climate action, enabling cities and regions to track efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and build resilience to climate change.</p> <p>The reporting process encourages cities and regions to better understand and reflect about the climate risks they face. Reporting also helps them to embed climate action planning in policy-making and spending and motivates them to create comprehensive action plans.</p> <p>Cities and regions only report once, through the CDP portal, and the publicly reported data is automatically shared with ICLEI. The reporting process is free, and the publicly reported data can be freely accessed online through CDP’s Open Data Portal.</p> <p>Local and regional governments give their permission to both ICLEI and CDP to use their publicly reported data and receive the support of both organizations. ICLEI uses this data to inform research and analysis activities and to represent local and regional governments on the global stage through high level political advocacy work. CDP uses the reported data to produce analytics and snapshot reports for local and regional governments, allowing them to track their progress and benchmark themselves against their peers. Both organizations encourage local and regional governments to report publicly as this strengthens subnational data and contributes to transparency and good governance.</p> <p>The online questionnaire is annually updated. In 2021, it was composed of 15 sections encompassing topics such as climate adaptation and mitigation actions, GHG emissions inventory, emissions reduction targets, energy efficiency and renewable energy targets, food systems, buildings, waste management and water security.</p>
<p>Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)</p>	<p>The GCoM has grown to be the largest global alliance for city climate leadership, built upon the commitment of 11,500+ cities and local governments, from 6 continents and 142 countries, sharing a long-term vision for combatting climate change.</p>
<p>References</p>	<p>What is the Global Covenant of Mayors? https://www.globalcovenantofmayors.org/who-we-are/</p>

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	https://www.globalcovenantofmayors.org/faq-landing/ Differences between MyCovenant and the CDP-ICLEI Unified Reporting System: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1_QpsXGHvyPbqKc528H_qkabmKTylfvD-/view
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No. of Network/ initiative	3
Network name	ManagEnergy - Energy Agencies leading the energy transition
Network website	https://www.managenergy.net/
Number of Members	358 local and regional energy agencies
Countries coverage	31 countries
Description of network	<p>ManagEnergy is a European Commission initiative (first launched in 2002) with the objectives of supporting regional and local energy agencies in becoming leaders in the energy transition and of increasing sustainable energy investments in regions and cities. It provides information, know-how and networking opportunities.</p> <p>ManagEnergy offers support to Energy Agencies through the following services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Master Classes: A tailor-made 3-day programme in Brussels, delivered by leading energy experts and targeting senior and management level energy agency staff. • Expert Missions: Providing know-how to energy agencies in the field of energy efficiency financing in their own region/city. • Networking Events: Annual networking events organized to increase cooperation, knowledge and peer exchange between energy agencies across Europe. • ManagEnergy Talks: A range of Public Talks held in the evenings to inform interested stakeholders about the latest developments in energy efficiency financing and project development.
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	ManagEnergy is based on the idea that more energy efficiency and renewable energy investments are needed at the regional / local level in Europe. Therefore, it places Energy Agencies at the forefront of energy investments in Europe, as through their role of project developers, aggregators and facilitators for public authorities, they are in a unique position to support the energy transition in their regions and cities.

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	ManagEnergy consortium is led by Limerick Institute of Technology (LIT) and includes Energy Agencies in Europe (North West Croatia - HR, Upper Austria - AT, Berlin - DE, Tipperary - IE), FEDARENE - a network of Energy Agencies in Europe (BE), COGNITA (HR) - an IT and e-Learning company and Millenium Promotion (HR) - a communications and PR team.
Introduced tool / methodology / digital platform for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	-
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	In the period 2017-2020 many of the above events were organized and information is available on ManagEnergy website. Between 2001 and 2015 ManagEnergy organized 45 capacity building workshops in EU Member States and 33 networking events.
References	https://www.managenergy.net/MasterClasses https://www.managenergy.net/ExpertMissions https://www.managenergy.net/NetworkingEvents https://www.managenergy.net/ManagEnergyTalks

No. of Network/ initiative	4
Network name	Clean energy for EU islands
Network website	https://clean-energy-islands.ec.europa.eu/
Number of Members	76 islands, 29 with published Clean Energy Transition Agendas / Plans
Countries coverage	14 EU countries with large island populations (Croatia, Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Spain, and Sweden)
Description of network	As part of the 'Clean energy for all Europeans' package, the Clean energy for EU islands initiative , launched in 2017, provides a long-term framework to help islands generate their own sustainable, low-cost energy. The initiative builds on a political declaration, signed by the European Commission and 14 EU countries with large island populations (Croatia, Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France,

	<p>Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Spain, and Sweden). As a follow-up, the parties also signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) in June 2020, to establish a long-term framework for cooperation to advance the energy transition and identify best practices on challenges that cannot be addressed at island-level.</p> <p>In 2018, the European Commission, in cooperation with the European Parliament, set up the Clean energy for EU islands secretariat to deliver the objectives of the Clean energy for EU islands initiative.</p>
<p>Introduced governance structure / figure for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clean energy for EU islands secretariat: central platform for the clean ET of more than 2,200 inhabited European islands (best practices, policy/ regulatory issues, dedicated advice for capacity building and clean energy transitioning). • Memorandum of Understanding between the EC and 14 EU countries with island populations to establish a long-term framework for cooperation to advance ET • Forums, regularly organised in combination with technical fairs, provide EU islands and other EU initiatives the opportunity to share best practices and show innovative projects in the areas of RES, EE and innovation.
<p>Introduced tool / methodology / digital platform for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clean Energy Transition Agenda (CETA) template (docx). Strategic roadmap for the local community transition process towards clean energy. • Islands Transition Handbook - detailed guidance on how to develop a CETA • Self-assessment Tool (excel): It helps islands to evaluate the current status of their clean energy transition according to eight indicators (e.g. energy vision, stakeholders' commitment, project opportunities etc.)
<p>Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)</p>	<p>Since the launch of the initiative, the Community now includes 76 islands, 29 of which have published Clean Energy Transition Agendas / Plans.</p>
<p>References</p>	<p>https://clean-energy-islands.ec.europa.eu/ https://clean-energy-islands.ec.europa.eu/about Clean Energy Transition Agenda (CETA) template: https://clean-energy-islands.ec.europa.eu/insights/publications/ceta-template Islands Transition Handbook: https://clean-energy-islands.ec.europa.eu/insights/publications/islands-transition-handbook Self-assessment Tool: https://clean-energy-islands.ec.europa.eu/node/327</p>

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No. of Network/ initiative	5
Network name	Energee-Watch: The European Network of Regional GhG Emissions and Energy Watch
Network website	https://energee-watch.eu/
Number of Members	20 members
Countries coverage	11 countries
Description of network	ENERGee WATCH is a European network of GhG Emissions observation and gives its name to a European project of peer-to-peer learning program enabling regional and local authorities to properly define, monitor and verify their sustainable actions.
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	Regional Energy and GhG Emissions observatories contribute towards building a representation of the regional impact on climate change and helps to identify regional areas of responsibilities and supports prioritizing actions. Regional observatories can fulfil diverse tasks, generally they provide data (most often free of charge) and knowledge about the region related to climate change. The provided data can cover a wide variety of topics like energy, emissions, air quality, social, economic or environmental effects.
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	Members of the Energee Watch network and mentors of the project all have tools to inform energy transition policies and monitor their implementation on their territories.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	
References	ENERGee Watch - overview of regional observatories: https://energee-watch.eu/observatories/

No. of Network/ initiative	6
Network name	DAFNI
Network website	https://dafninetwerk.gr/
Number of Members	DAFNI Network counts 56 members of which 52 island Municipalities, the Regions of North Aegean, South Aegean, Ionian Islands and the Regional Union of Municipalities of the Ionian Islands.
Countries coverage	Greece
Description of network	DAFNI - Network of Sustainable Greek Islands is a non-profit organization of island local and regional authorities. Founded in 2006.
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	Supporting, empowering local government, raising awareness and actively involving citizens in the implementation of projects with a positive impact for local development in areas such as: green energy, environment, sustainable tourism, circular economy, sustainable mobility, education and employment.
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	DAFNI aims to strengthen island local governance and help islands embark on a sustainable development paradigm, through the integrated management of natural resources and infrastructures , the uptake of sustainable tourism and the enhanced interdependence of the primary, secondary and tertiary sectors .
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p>Several projects have been initiated by DAFNI.</p> <p>Among them are initiatives such as the “Pact of Islands” and the “Smart Islands Initiative”, as well as the Smart Islands Education. The aim of the Smart Islands Education initiative is to create a network of teachers with strong action both in the school and in the local community of the island, willing to get in touch with innovative technologies and practices for the sustainable management of the infrastructure of the islands through their participation in Of Greece.</p> <p>The program was attended by 10 secondary school teachers from a number of Greek islands (Rhodes, Tinos, Cephalonia, Crete etc.)</p>

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	DAFNI also provided technical support to the Municipal Service for water supply and sewage in order to promote all the necessary studies for the construction of a wind farm with a capacity of 1.8 MW at Agia Marina in the Municipality of Kos.
References	https://dafninetwerk.gr/technikh-yposthriksh/

No. of Network/ initiative	7
Network name	Greening the islands
Network website	http://www.greeningtheislands.net/
Number of Members	20
Countries coverage	TANZANIA, GREECE, MALDIVES, ITALY, MALTA, GERMANY, TUNISIA, SPAIN, ESTONIA, CROATIA, UNITED KINGDOM, CAPE VERT.
Description of network	Greening The Islands matches islands needs with innovative solutions and facilitates the origination of projects for the sustainable transition of islands and their replicability on the mainland by acting as a catalyst in relationships between governments, business, academia and citizens, disseminating knowledge and best practices.
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greening the Islands Observatory • Greening the Islands App: The online islands' scientific community • Greening the Islands Awards Regulation 2021 • Greening the Islands Academy • Disseminating knowledge and best practices
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	<p>The Greening the Islands Observatory aggregates key stakeholders to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Match island needs and innovative sustainable solutions • Produce reports & studies to address strategies and policies • Originate projects, business models and financing opportunities • Promote the cooperation between governments and corporates
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	The Greening the Islands Observatory was launched at the 2018 Greening the Islands international conference of Minorca.
References	http://www.greeningtheislands.net/index.php/observatory-home/

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No. of Network/ initiative	8
Network name	CRETAN ENERGY CLUSTER
Network website	https://cretanenergycluster.gr/
Number of Members	The Cluster includes 10 companies which employ more than 140 people.
Countries coverage	Greece
Description of network	<p>The CRETAN ENERGY CLUSTER is a small cluster for renewable energies and environmental technologies. It provides services for green-tech companies in the field of renewable energy and energy efficiency technologies, and it is located in Crete, Greece.</p> <p>In order to strengthen and extend his position, the CRETAN ENERGY CLUSTER is supporting member companies as a personal business partner through innovation and R&D support, international marketing and access to new markets.</p>
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	<p>CRETAN ENERGY CLUSTER companies are becoming stronger and more competitive because:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They operate in an organized network that facilitates communication across the chain to optimize business services and final costs; • They increase their skills thanks to the transfer of knowledge at the productive level to competitiveness and cooperation; • They can take advantage of the close relationship with institutes, research groups & communities, centers of excellence and major research centers.
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	<p>CRETAN ENERGY CLUSTER aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The organized promotion of RES systems; • The emergence of our natural energy resources; • Informing and educating our members about new markets; • The communication with local educational institutions and public bodies; • Organized contact with suppliers.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	Slow pace of expanding the network with new project initiatives and new members.
References	https://cretanenergycluster.gr/el/profil

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No. of Network/ initiative	9
Network name	Smart Islands Initiative
Network website	http://smartislandsinitiative.eu/en/index.php
Number of Members	42 public bodies 12 private bodies 26 Community Support Organisations
Countries coverage	12 countries: Croatia, Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Malta, Netherlands
Description of network	<p>The Smart Islands Initiative founded in 2016 conveys the significant potential of islands to function as laboratories for technological, social, environmental, economic and political innovation, offering higher quality of life to local communities and helping Europe become a sustainable and inclusive economy.</p> <p>The added value of the Initiative is that it is bottom-up, driven by and for Europe’s island authorities and communities. Experience shows that if empowered, local actors are in a position to shape policies and mature projects that are reflective of local conditions, thus more effective and successful in the long-run.</p>
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	On 28 March 2017, 33 island representatives came together in the European Parliament to sign on behalf of over 200 islands the Smart islands Declaration , cornerstone document of the Initiative. Hosted by 12 Members of European Parliament, the event was attended by EU policy makers, utilities and service operators, market players and citizen groups, who acknowledged the Smart Islands Initiative as a meaningful vehicle for islands’ transition to a low-carbon, smart and sustainable future.
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	<p>Through the above initiative, a multilevel governance project was produced titled “SMILEGOV” (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCp8B9dW0TnOaoiLp2VuG3hw).</p> <p>Similar to this initiative with several relevant deliverables is also the Horizon2020 project titled “SMart IsLand Energy systems” with the acronym: “SMILE” with a library containing policy recommendations for energy planning in island areas.</p>

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Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	In 2018 the Network numbered 150 members, 11 clusters, 250 trainees and developed drafts of 61 bankable projects.
References	<p>Smart islands Declaration: https://smartislandsinitiative.eu/pdf/Smart_Islands_Declaration.pdf</p> <p>Lessons learned with regards to governance of the energy transition: https://europeansmallislands.files.wordpress.com/2015/11/smilegov-lessons-learned.pdf</p>

No. of Network/ initiative	10
Network name	Pact of Islands
Network website	https://www.islepact.eu/
Number of Members	64 insular communities signed the Pact of Islands
Countries coverage	9 countries involved in the partnership: UK, Portugal, Cyprus, Greece, Sweden, Spain, Malta, Italy, Denmark
Description of network	<p>The Pact of Islands is a political initiative of European island municipalities and regions aiming at reducing island carbon dioxide emissions by 20% by 2020. The Pact was developed in line with the Covenant of Mayors. It was adopted in 2011 with the support of the European Commission and the European Parliament, and is addressed to island authorities wishing to make a real commitment to the European effort to tackle climate change.</p> <p>The commitments undertaken by a Municipality upon signing the Pact of Islands are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To record CO₂ emissions for the municipality's territory; • To develop a Sustainable Energy Action Plan to go beyond the EU targets of reducing CO₂ emissions by at least 20%; • To prepare and regularly submit reports pertaining to the evaluation, monitoring and verification of the action plan's implementation; • To work together with the European Commission to organise information events on the intelligent use of energy.

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Introduced governance structure / figure for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	The recognition of the role of island communities in the mobilisation against global warming by the European Parliament which in its Declaration 37/2011 recognised the Pact of Islands as an EU initiative parallel to the Covenant of Mayors.
Introduced tool / methodology / digital platform for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	A number of software tools and methodologies to help new signatories develop their own energy models, Island Sustainable Energy Plans (ISEAPs) and Bankable Projects.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p>On 25 June 2015, the second formal signing ceremony of the Pact of Islands was held in Brussels during the annual General Meeting of CPMR (Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions) Islands Commission.</p> <p>More than 117 islands participate in the Pact of Islands, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 27 Greek island municipalities (30 islands) and 3 island regions; • 56 Islands Sustainable Energy Action Plans were completed • 53 project proposals analysed (12 are already on-going); • 20 are in negotiations with banks/investors; • 21 are project ideas that will be proposed for financing. <p>These projects have the potential to save more than 18 million tonnes of CO₂ per year, equivalent to more than 30% of the total CO₂ emissions of Denmark in 2010. This number represents a combined 25% CO₂ emissions reduction for the 53 insular communities that have already finalised and are in the process of implementing their ISEAPs, meeting the main objective of the project, i.e. to reduce CO₂ emissions by at least 20% by 2020.</p>
References	https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/DCL-7-2011-0037_EL.pdf

5.3 Governance status within the pilot territories

The following tables present a review of the governance status in relation to **energy transition**, in the 3 ePLANET pilot territories (**Region of Crete-Greece, Province of Girona-Region of Catalonia-Spain, Zlín Region -Czech Republic**), including:

- Public authorities, including the type and format of data required to be collected;
- Existing **governance structures / figures** coordinating and monitoring energy transition plans and actions in the pilot territories (i.e. any institutionalized structures e.g. Regional or national energy transition committees, boards, etc. or individuals e.g. Region / Municipalities energy manager, CoM regional or Municipal coordinator etc.) and the **degree of multi-level governance coordination** on energy transition between National level, Regions and Municipalities;
- **Tools / methodologies / digital platforms** used in the pilot territories for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities, including the type and format of information/data required to be collected.

The implementation status is also described, e.g. progress, delays, possible barriers towards coordinated energy transition.

5.3.1 Pilot territory 1: Region of Crete (Greece)

Pilot territory (1) - Region of Crete (Greece)	
<p>Description of <i>governance structure / figure</i> coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)</p>	<p><u>Local (Municipal) level</u></p> <p><u>CoM contact persons</u></p> <p>18 Municipalities in the Region of Crete are signatories of the CoM, 16 of which have already prepared and submitted a Sustainable Energy Action Plan. Only 4 of them are in the phase of monitoring their SEAP and have submitted monitoring/progress reports.</p> <p>The Mayor is the formal signatory of the Covenant, and there are also designated CoM contact persons from the Municipality (typically a public officer of the planning department, technical department, development department etc, or in many cases, an external specialist consultant supporting the Municipality in the development and monitoring of its action plan).</p> <p><u>Energy managers of Municipal buildings</u></p> <p>In line with Greek legislation, all public authorities must designate an Energy Manager for each public building under the public authority's administrative jurisdiction (one person can be the manager of more than one buildings). Municipalities of Crete have appointed Energy Managers for their public buildings. They are responsible for collecting and monitoring energy data for the buildings under their responsibility, including energy efficiency</p>

	<p>measures applied or planned to be applied, and report annually to the Ministry of Environment and Energy using specific monitoring tools provided by the Ministry (see below).</p> <p><u>Regional level</u></p> <p>The Regional Development Fund of Crete (RDFC) - Regional Energy Agency of Crete, is a Regional CoM Coordinator, signatory of the Pact of Islands, Member of the Clean Energy for Islands initiative, Member of ManagEnergy. It is a supporting entity to the Region of Crete development planning (including energy planning). RDFC supports both the Region and the 24 Municipalities of Crete with energy advice, through the Regional Energy Agency of Crete (REAC) operated by RDFC. RDFC has supported 7 Municipalities of Crete in the development, implementation and monitoring of their SEAPs.</p> <p><u>Energy managers of Regional buildings</u></p> <p>In line with Greek legislation, the Region of Crete has appointed Energy Managers for its public buildings. They are responsible for collecting and monitoring energy data for the buildings under their responsibility, including energy efficiency measures applied or planned to be applied, and report annually to the Ministry of Environment and Energy using specific monitoring tools provided by the Ministry (see below).</p> <p><u>National level</u></p> <p>The Ministry of Environment & Energy is the responsible Government authority in Greece for all issues related to energy policy and energy transition at national level.</p> <p>CRES is the National CoM coordinator in Greece, with institutional role to provide technical support to local/regional authorities to prepare energy efficiency plans and actions and support to the Ministry of Environment & Energy for implementing energy efficiency policy.</p> <p><u>Energy managers of Central government buildings</u></p> <p>In line with Greek legislation, Ministries and other central government authorities have appointed Energy Managers for their public buildings. They are responsible for collecting & monitoring energy data for the buildings under their responsibility, including energy efficiency measures applied or planned to be applied, and report annually to the Ministry of Environment and Energy using specific monitoring tools provided by the Ministry (see below).</p>
<p>Description of <i>tools / methodologies / digital platforms</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities</p>	<p><u>Tools:</u></p> <p>[1] 16 Sustainable Energy (and Climate) Action Plans (SEAPs / SECAPs) of Municipalities in the Region of Crete, in the framework of the Covenant of Mayors initiative (described in section 3.1 element 9 above).</p> <p>[2] Energy Efficiency Plans for Regional and Municipal buildings</p>

	<p>In line with Greek legislation, regional and local public authorities, must conduct, for public buildings under their jurisdiction, Energy Efficiency plans for their public-building stock, to be monitored, updated and submitted to the Ministry of Environment and Energy every 2 years. The Ministry has issued a template of the Energy Efficiency plan (see ‘References’).</p> <p>[3] National Energy and Climate Plan (described in section 3.1 element 7 above).</p> <p><u>Digital platforms for reporting/monitoring:</u></p> <p>[1] The 16 Municipalities in Crete that have SE(C)APs use the CoM MyCovenant platform for reporting and monitoring their plans.</p> <p>[2] Excel-based Energy reporting and monitoring tool for Energy Managers of public buildings, developed by the Ministry of Environment & Energy (see ‘References’). Energy managers must collect and insert in the tool information for buildings under their responsibility: key technical characteristics (building envelope & services) that affect energy performance, actual energy consumption data, energy saving measures applied or planned to be applied etc. They have to complete the Excel tool and send the completed tools by email to the Ministry of Environment & Energy on an annual basis. A corresponding e-platform is under development by the Ministry, to further automate the process and allow central collection and monitoring of the information.</p>
<p>Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)</p>	<p><u>Progress-Barriers-delays:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 18 Municipalities in the Region of Crete are signatories of the CoM, 16 of which have already prepared and submitted a SE(C)AP, and 4 of them are in the phase of monitoring their SEAP and have submitted monitoring/progress reports. • Information on the actual data uploaded by Municipalities on the MyCovenant platform or the offline Excel files used, is not publicly available and is not available to CRES or RDFC, despite being regional and national CoM coordinator respectively. Only summary information and KPIs for each SE(C)AP is publicly available from the CoM website. Contact with each Municipality would be required in order to obtain detailed information, and in many cases it may not be easily found, as SE(C)APs were prepared by external consultants, without strong involvement of Municipality personnel. • Information on the progress of how many Municipalities of Crete have prepared and issued Energy Efficiency plans for their public buildings (in line with legislation requirements) to the Ministry of Energy is not publicly available and is not available to CRES or RDFC. Contact with each Municipality would be required in order to obtain it, and in many cases it may not be easily found, as the plans may have been prepared by external consultants, without strong involvement of Municipality personnel.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There have been delays by public authorities in appointing designated Energy Managers for their public buildings, and since appointed, only some of them have been undertaking the process of regular collection and monitoring of information using the Excel-based tool and sending it to the Ministry of Environment. Information from the Excel-tools is not collected centrally by the Region, for the Regional buildings and for all Municipal buildings. • Through previously implemented Interreg MED project SHERPA, an Energy Efficiency Roadmap was prepared for the territory of Crete, including all information that was possible to be collected for both Regional and Municipal buildings, in order to undertake integrated planning, however the Roadmap did not evolve into a formally approved policy, that would be updated and monitored in future. There was a proposal for setting up a formal governance structure (e.g. committee responsible for energy management of public buildings, with representatives of both the Region and all 24 Municipalities), however this was not set up as a formal structure and does not currently operate. • Despite the e-platform for energy managers having been pre-announced since a few years now by the Ministry of Environment & Energy, it has still not been released; hence there is lack of automatic central coordination of the collected information. <p>As can be concluded from the above, there is limited multi-level governance coordination on energy transition between national-regional-local level in the pilot territory of Crete, and significant room for improvement through the e-PLANET project activities.</p>
References	<p>Excel-based Energy reporting and monitoring tool for energy managers of public buildings, Ministry of Environment and Energy, url-GR: https://ypen.gov.gr/energeia/energeiaki-exoikonomisi/ktiria/energeiakoi-ypefthynoi/</p> <p>https://ypen.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/FKE.xlsx</p> <p>Template for Energy Efficiency plans for Regional and Municipal buildings, Ministry of Environment and Energy</p> <p>https://ypen.gov.gr/energeia/energeiaki-exoikonomisi/ktiria/schedio-energeiakis-apodosis-ktirion-perifereion-kai-dimon/</p>

5.3.2 Pilot territory 2: Province of Girona (Catalonia, Spain)

Pilot territory (2) - Province of Girona (Catalonia, Spain)	
<p>Description of <i>governance structure / figure</i> coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)</p>	<p><u>Local (Municipal) level</u></p> <p><u>CoM contact persons</u></p> <p>210 Municipalities in the Region of Girona are signatories of the CoM, 201 of which are redacting their SECAP that it will be submitted by the end of May.</p> <p>The Mayor is the formal signatory of the Covenant, and there are also designated CoM contact persons from the Municipality (typically a public officer of the planning department, technical department, development department etc, or in many cases, an Energy Transition Technician supporting the Municipality in anything related in energy through the Energy Transition Offices (OTE)).</p> <p><u>Energy Transition Offices (OTE)</u></p> <p>Girona Region has 7 county councils and 3 of them have an Energy Transition Office, but in the future, the idea is to implement an OTE to each county council. At least, in each OTE there is an Energy Transition Technician to help municipalities with anything related to energy and the environment.</p> <p><u>National level</u></p> <p>The Ministry for the ecological transition and demographic challenge is de responsible Government authority in Spain for all issues related to energy policy and energy transition and at the level of the autonomous community of Catalonia the authorized entity is ICAEN</p> <p>Diputació de Girona is the National CoM coordinator in Girona, with institutional role to provide technical support to Municipalities authorities to prepare energy efficiency plans and actions.</p>
<p>Description of <i>tools / methodologies / digital platforms</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities</p>	<p><u>Tools:</u></p> <p>[1] 201 Sustainable Energy (and Climate) Action Plans (SECAPs) of Municipalities in the Region of Girona, in the framework of the Covenant of Mayors imitative.</p> <p>[2] European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), local section 2014-2020</p> <p>With regard to the local world, the ERDF OP also provides for actions promoted by local authorities within the framework of priority axis 4, which aims to encourage the transition to a low-carbon economy in all sectors; and priority axis 6, which aims to conserve and protect the environment and promote resource efficiency.</p>

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Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 201 Municipalities are redacting their SECAP that it will be submitted by the end of May • Within the European Regional Development Fund Operative Program for Catalonia it has implemented to Install 7 biomass boilers, build 15 biomass heat networks and build 2 buildings for forest biomass treatment. <p>Diputació de Girona - (ddgi.cat)</p>
References	<p>Monitoring web for Biomass boilers consumptions</p> <p>ForestHEAT</p>

5.3.3 Pilot territory 3: Zlín Region (Czech Republic)

Pilot territory (3) - Zlín Region (Czech Republic)	
<p>Description of <i>governance structure / figure</i> coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)</p>	<p><u>Municipal and regional level</u></p> <p>The Zlín Region is a frontier region with both agriculture and industrial tradition and a great density of settlements. There are 307 local authorities, with a population of 580.119 inhabitants (2021).</p> <p>The ET vertical governance in Zlín Region is solid and well-established. Energy transition strategy in the region is mainly defined by EAZK, and later adopted by the region. Local authorities implement the ET rather through planning particular projects and individual implementation, hardly any of them have a real SEAP.</p> <p>There are 307 municipalities in the Zlín Region and EAZK also supports both the region and the municipalities to gain financial sources from existing funds to implement EE measures and increase the RES share on energy supply in the Zlín Region. The vast majority of the projects initialised and administered by the EAZK have been financed with the support of structural funds. Only in 2019 EAZK processed 35 investment EE and RES projects for the Zlín Region and municipalities of the Zlín Region with the total value 253,7 mio CZK (app. 9,8 mio EUR).</p> <p><u>National level</u></p> <p>In the case of the Czech Republic the Czech Republic's national plan in the field of energy and climate was prepared and approved by the Czech government in November 2019. In terms of more specific energy transition plans and measures, this issue is assessed from a regional perspective, from where it is easier to join together particular stakeholders from a larger area, to communicate with the national level and, at the same time to reach effectively even the smallest municipalities.</p> <p>However, relevant stakeholders in financing the energy transition are on national level and they are mainly ministries and their</p>

	<p>institutions that participate in developing the national legislation in this topic as well as administrate financial support in energy efficiency. They are mainly:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ministry of Environment which is responsible for development and managing of the OP Environment, National Programme Environment and New Green Savings Programme. - State Environmental Fund of the Czech Republic which is an intermediating body managing the operational phase of the OP Environment implementation, announces call for proposals, evaluates projects submitted, is supervising project implementation and communicates with applicants on day-to day basis.” - Ministry of Trade and Industry - which is responsible for development and management of the Operational Programme Enterprise and Innovations for Competitiveness and EFEKT Programme. - Ministry of Regional Development - which is responsible for development and management of the Integrated Regional Operational Programme (IROP).
<p>Description of <i>tools / methodologies / digital platforms</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities</p>	<p>EAZK operates within the whole area of the Zlín Region which is identical with NUTS3-CZ072. The EAZK is a project partner with a great potential to address various target groups as the agency provides energy management for more than 150 organisations established both by the Zlín Region and particular municipalities.</p> <p>Energy agency operates also as an independent advisor for municipalities of the Zlín Region in their process of development of their own SEAPS. The agency acts as a negotiator between politicians and municipalities on one side and consultancy companies, central heating systems operators and energy suppliers on the other side. Expected results include new/improved municipal Energy plans for increase of energy efficiency, and RES utilization, balanced and reliable energy supply.</p> <p>Thanks to its nature EAZK has the accessibility to all reliable regional databases and documents on the potential of the Zlín Region. EAZK also participates in suggesting and implementation of strategic documents and policies of the Zlín Region in the field of energy, environment, and innovations. Representatives of the agency are involved in the process of consultation and suggesting of national legislative documents and policies as members of various committees and working groups both on regional and national level.</p> <p>EAZK disposes of a rich experience in the field of defining the needs of towns and villages of the Zlín Region. This experience has been gained during 14 years of agency activities when many conceptual documents both for region and municipalities were developed and implemented with considerable contribution of EAZK.</p>
<p>Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)</p>	<p>There is a margin to improve horizontal governance of energy transition in the region. There are no signatories of Covenant of Mayors at local level (EAZK is supporting partner since 2014), and most of the energy efficiency measures rely on the effectiveness</p>

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	and active support of EAZK to adapt local level policies and goals to the energy transition. The capacity building of local officers, the deployment of a horizontal governance framework for local authorities, and the deployment of a sharing information platform will foster the multi-level governance of the region.
References	Home - Energetická agentura Zlínského kraje, o.p.s. (eazk.cz)

5.4 Best practices from past or ongoing projects

The following tables present a review of **best practices on multi-level governance for energy transition** that the ePLANET partners have identified from **past or ongoing projects** (national / EU projects) that they have participated in (or beyond), including:

- Best practices on introduced **governance structures / figures** coordinating and monitoring energy transition plans and actions between **National level, Regions and Municipalities** (i.e. institutionalized structures or individuals etc.);
- Best practices on produced **tools / methodologies / digital platforms** for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities.

The main objectives of the provided elements are described as well as the implementation status e.g. progress, expected or achieved impacts and possible barriers.

No. of Project	1
Project full title/acronym	Integrated Management Support for Energy Efficiency in Mediterranean Public Buildings - IMPULSE
Funding Programme	Interreg MED 2014-2020
Project website	https://impulse.interreg-med.eu/
Project status (ongoing / completed)	Completed
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	-
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET	<p>Methodology:</p> <p>An integrated methodology (composed of a series of Excel-based tools) to support public authorities in the MED area in the development of oriented action plans for energy efficiency of public buildings at local level. The methodology was developed to</p>

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projects by public authorities	<p>support public authorities in addressing the requirements of Article 7 of L.4342/2015 (Greek transposition of Article 5 of 2012/27/EU) on the exemplary role of public buildings and the need to conduct energy-efficiency action plans for public buildings.</p> <p>Digital platform:</p> <p>Excel-based user-friendly platform for data-base creation of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for alternative retrofit scenarios for large samples of public buildings. The platform aims to facilitate public authorities in assessing the expected energy, environmental and economic implications of alternative retrofitting investments ranging from small-scale to deep interventions of energy upgrading for various public-building typologies.</p>
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p>By adopting the IMPULSE methodology, the 6 pilot Mediterranean Municipalities of Heraklion-Greece, Elche-Spain, Cannes-France, Ravenna-Italy, Osijek-Croatia and Mostar-Bosnia & Herzegovina, as active partners in the IMPULSE project completed a mature plan for gradual energy renovation projects in the next years.</p> <p>Using the IMPULSE platform, KPIs' databases for various retrofitting scenarios were produced for the 6 pilot Municipalities.</p>
References	<p>IMPULSE methodology booklet (EN)</p> <p>Integrated public-buildings energy-efficiency plans for 6 pilot Mediterranean Municipalities:</p> <p>IMPULSE building typologies and performance indicators platforms (refer to the D3.4.1 platform)</p> <p>Simulated results and hierarchy of retrofitting measures for Heraklion-Greece, url-ENG/GR</p>

No. of Project	2
Project full title/acronym	SHared knowledge for Energy Renovation in buildings by Public Administrations - SHERPA
Funding Programme	Interreg MED 2014-2020
Project website	https://sherpa.interreg-med.eu/

Project status (<i>ongoing / completed</i>)	Completed
Introduced governance structure / figure for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	<p>During the implementation of SHERPA, there was a proposal for setting up a formal governance structure to coordinate energy efficiency plans and actions for public buildings, coordinated by each SHERPA participating Region, with the participation of all respective Municipalities in the territory of the Region. In the Region of Crete (partner of SHERPA), the proposal was for such a <u>Committee</u> that would be coordinated by the Region, with the participation of energy managers of Regional buildings, designated personnel from the Region technical, development & financial departments, and participation of designated representatives from all 24 Municipalities of Crete (e.g. CoM contact person in each Municipality, energy managers of Municipal buildings etc.)</p> <p>Eventually this governance structure was not set up as a formal deliverable of SHERPA, so in the case of the Region of Crete, it was not formally set up and does not currently operate. Such a structure could be further explored within the ePLANET activities.</p>
Introduced tool / methodology / digital platform for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	<p><u>Methodology - Tool:</u></p> <p>The project supported coordinated regional & local strategies for improving the energy efficiency of public buildings, through a shared information system, coordinated governance, training & financing strategies. The objective was to create integrated Regional Energy Renovation of Buildings (ERB) Roadmaps, in a coordinated multi-governance level approach assessing the existing status and identifying actions for both Regional and Municipal buildings in the territory of Crete.</p> <p><u>Digital platforms:</u></p> <p>[1] SHERPA Shared Information System. Digital platform developed by CIMNE and used during the Testing (pilot) phase of the project, to facilitate the participating partner Regions in collecting, comparing, benchmarking, information for the energy consumption and energy saving measures for their public buildings. For the Region of Crete, information was entered in this platform for the 10 pilot Regional buildings assessed in the Testing phase. The platform is no longer operational by CIMNE.</p> <p>[2] SHERPA Capitalisation platform. An online platform developed by CRES (coordinator of SHERPA Capitalisation WP) as a “hub” of useful information available to all interested public authorities and stakeholders, operational beyond the end of SHERPA, including a searchable database of deliverables, best practices, tools, methodologies, from SHERPA and other relevant MED/EU projects and initiatives in the thematic of energy efficiency of buildings. Access to the platform is free.</p> <p>The platform is structured around 4 thematic Capitalisation Toolkits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical • Financial • Awareness <p>representing the holistic methodology introduced by the SHERPA project for addressing energy renovation of public buildings (See 'References').</p>
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	By adopting the SHERPA methodology, 8 Regional Energy Renovation of Buildings (ERB) Roadmaps were developed, for the participating Mediterranean partner Regions (Catalonia-Spain, Crete-Greece, Valencia-Spain, Emilia-Romagna-Italy, Lazio-Italy, Abruzzo-Italy, Gozo-Malta, Dubrovnik-Neretva- Croatia).
References	SHERPA Capitalisation Platform & Thematic Capitalisation Toolkits: http://sherpanet.eu/ http://sherpanet.eu/forumdisplay.php?fid=3

No. of Project	3
Project full title/acronym	Building Information aGgregation, harmonization and analytics platform/BIGG
Funding Programme	H2020
Project website	https://www.bigg-project.eu/
	<p>The image shows the BIGG logo on the left, which consists of a stylized bar chart with the text 'BIGG BUILDING INFORMATION AGGREGATION' below it. On the right is a screenshot of the BIGG website, featuring a city skyline at night and the text 'BIGG Building Information aGgregation, harmonization and analytics platform' with a 'Discover More' button.</p>
Project status (ongoing / completed)	Ongoing (1/12/2020 to 30/11/2023)
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	<p>The BIGG project aims at demonstrating the application of big data technologies and data analytic techniques for the complete buildings life-cycle of more than 4,000 buildings in Catalonia and Greece pilots</p> <p><u>Catalan pilot site:</u></p> <p>The main actors identified within the Catalan institution are:</p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • around 100 energy managers, responsible for the management of public buildings having a weekly or monthly interaction with the energy management tool, • around 20 to 30 policy makers responsible for planning actions to improve energy performance of buildings with a monthly or bi annually interaction with the tool, and • about 10 public authorities on special interest on general building trends, having semiannual or annual interaction with the management tool. <p>The Datasets that will be used to facilitate this business case, provided by some partners are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic systems description, energy consumptions and EEM for 4000 public buildings of the Catalan government. • Monitoring data of 272 Catalan public buildings. • Equipment inventory, preventive and corrective maintenance actions of these 272 buildings. • Control data of HVAC systems for 40 public buildings. • Spanish Municipal data. <p><u>Greek pilot site:</u></p> <p>The Greek pilots are divided into different business cases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The first ones focus on 17 large commercial office buildings in Athens managed through Energy Performance Contracting (EPC) and Maintenance Contract. The pilot site will demonstrate the application of EPC-based management for commercial buildings, whose main objective will be continuously optimizing the building operation consumption, to guarantee the comfort of occupants, by controlling HVAC systems/lighting. • The second scenario will focus on delivering flexibility services by managing appliances of residential and commercial consumers of electricity and natural gas, spread across various cities of Greece (Athens, Thessaloniki, Volos and others).
Introduced tool / methodology / digital platform for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	<p>A Big Data TOOL with AI will allow making decisions for de-risking investments in energy transition projects (in buildings).</p> <p>Initially will contain information from 4000 buildings of Generalitat of Catalonia.</p> <p>PLATFORM: an open source Big-Data reference Architecture for collection, processing and exchanging data from different sources.</p>
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p>BIGG is a 36 months project, starting on 1/12/2021 and will end on 30/11/2023. At this moment it is at middle stage, having identified the business cases in both pilot sites. The project has also defined the architecture of the platform and works on the backend and frontend of the platform. Expected to be ready by the end of 2022.</p>
References	<p>BIGG Web url-EN: https://www.bigg-project.eu/</p>

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	<p>Catalan pilot url-EN: https://www.bigg-project.eu/bigg-project-pilots-business-cases-and-use-cases/</p> <p>Greek pilot url-EN: https://www.bigg-project.eu/bigg-project-pilots-business-cases-and-use-cases-in-greece/</p>
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No. of Project	4
Project full title/acronym	Energy Efficiency Performance-Tracking Platform for Benchmarking Savings and Investments in Buildings / EN-TRACK
Funding Programme	H2020
Project website	https://en-track.eu/
Project status (ongoing / completed)	Ongoing (1/11/2020 to 31/10/2023)
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	<p>EN-TRACK aims to enable a one-stop-shop platform to allow a better decision making of investments in energy efficiency projects in buildings.</p> <p>The platform will allow to make better decisions for de-risking investments in energy efficiency projects for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial institutions • Building owners
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	<p>The EN-TRACK platform will have several tools for different user levels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Public: Cross-sectional benchmarking tool to analyse: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy Efficiency Measures: ○ Building types • Data providers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Longitudinal benchmarking ○ Cross-sectional benchmarking

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Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	EN-TRACK is a 36 months project, starting on 1/11/2021 and will end on 30/10/2023. At this moment it is at middle stage, having defined the architecture of the platform and works on the backend and frontend of the platform to be ready on June 2022 for internal validation and public by autumn 2022.
References	Project website url-EN: https://en-track.eu/

No. of Project	5
Project full title/acronym	De-Risking Energy Efficiency Platform / DEEP-EEFIG
Funding Programme	European Commission's Directorate-General for Energy
Project website	https://deep.eefig.eu/
Project status (<i>ongoing / completed</i>)	Ongoing
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	The Energy Efficiency Financial Institutions Group (EEFIG) established in 2013 by the European Commission Directorate-General for Energy and the United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative (UNEP FI). EEFIG work is providing a significant contribution in accelerating private finance to energy efficiency.
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	<p>The EEFIG De-risking Energy Efficiency Platform (DEEP):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DEEP is an open-source database for energy efficiency investments performance monitoring and benchmarking. • DEEP provides an improved understanding of the real risks and benefits of energy efficiency investments by providing market evidence and investment track records. • Includes 15,000+ energy efficiency projects in buildings and industry from 30 data providers. • New data and improved functionality is added regularly.

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Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	EEFIG addresses barriers to energy efficiency financing through both policy design and market-based solutions to increase the scale of energy efficiency investments across Europe. Composed of over 300 representatives from more than 200 organisations, EEFIG's strength are its members - spanning public and private financial institutions, industry representatives and sector experts. EEFIG works through working groups that target specific themes. Through a multi-level stakeholder dialogue, working groups identify opportunities and barriers in the long-term financing for energy efficiency, and propose policy and market solutions.
References	EEFIG web url-EN: https://ec.europa.eu/eefig/index_en DEEP web url-EN: https://ec.europa.eu/eefig/going-activities_en DEEP platform url-EN: https://deep.eefig.eu/

No. of Project	6
Project full title/acronym	Boilers, heat networks and facilities for chip production / Bebiomassgi
Funding Programme	ERDF
Project website	https://www.ddgi.cat/web/servei/3372/calderes--xarxes-de-calor-i-instal-lacions-per-a-la-produccio-d-estella-operacio-go03-000003
Project status (ongoing / completed)	Completed
Introduced governance structure / figure for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	<u>Local Authorities/Municipalities:</u> 22 municipalities were involved in the project. 7 biomass boilers were installed, 15 biomass heat networks were constructed and 2 forest biomass treatment facilities were built. The project had a total cost of 3,982,391.24 euros, 50% of which was financed by ERDF funds, 24% by the Girona Provincial Council, and 26% by the municipalities involved.
Introduced tool / methodology / digital platform for multi-level	Each municipality details the project carried out with the following information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Action

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governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description • Year of execution • Cost of the investment, broken down by contribution of each governance structure • Savings in CO2 emissions • Energy savings • Renewable energy production • Percentage of energy savings
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	The project has launched a new project called ForesHEAT, which provides online monitoring of forest biomass consumption. A free service to monitor and manage biomass installations for municipalities, biomass suppliers or energy service companies.
References	Video results url-CAT: https://youtu.be/Lzf3V9YkFNA ForesHEAT url-CAT: https://www.forestheat.cat/

No. of Project	7
Project full title/acronym	Comunitats Locals d'Energia / Local Energy Communities
Funding Programme	Girona Provincial Council's Service Plan and Action Plan
Project website	-
Project status (<i>ongoing / completed</i>)	Ongoing
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	<p>Girona Provincial Council is promoting this pioneering project in Spain, offering technical and financial support to local councils that wish to promote local energy communities.</p> <p>Photovoltaic solar panels are installed on municipal facilities, supplying electricity to the buildings themselves, to homes in energy poverty and to all those who wish to join the community.</p>
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level	The Girona Provincial Council has drawn up a guide to facilitate the implementation of local energy communities in the territory:

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governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	Guide for the use of roofs and land for the local production of renewable energies.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	90 projects of energy local communities already done or started a project. Progress in 2022: 46 municipalities have initiated the drafting of these reports for the implementation of local energy communities and 27 more will start soon.
References	Guide url-CAT New project launch url-CAT New guide launch url-CAT

No. of Project	8
Project full title/acronym	Energy efficiency with Performance guarantees in the private and public sector, guarantEE
Funding Programme	Horizon 2020 (2016-2019)
Project website	https://guarantee-project.eu/
Project status (ongoing / completed)	Completed (1/4/2016 to 31/3/2019)
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	Introduced a new figure, “EPC facilitator” as a key driver to foster EPC contracts. Main function: to give guidance and advising in those installations willing to do energy equipment renovation, to be done using the EPC contracting Trainings conducted for the new EPC facilitators.
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	Developed an on-line TOOL for a pre-check of EPC availability. Methodology is the EPC contract model developed. No tools for governance of ET projects. For a certain set of Public buildings, the governance is done directly by EPC facilitator’s team of ICAEN.

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Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	
References	GuarantEE Precheck EPC tool: http://www.epccheck.eu/

No. of Project	9
Project full title/acronym	New finance for energy efficiency measures in Public Buildings New Finance
Funding Programme	Interreg MED 2014-2020
Project website	https://new-finance.interreg-med.eu/
Project status (<i>ongoing / completed</i>)	Completed (1/11/2016 to 30/4/2018)
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	This project did not have any target on governance or new figures. Project based on business models for energy efficiency implementation. The business models focused on different modalities of Energy Performance Contracting (EPC)
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	Methodology: based on EPC model contracting to implement energy efficiency projects and its finance. Financing SHERPA's Tool adopted.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	Signed contracts under EPC model to finance energy efficiency measures in Croatia, Bosnia, Slovenia, Italy and Catalonia.
References	EPC guide

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No. of Project	10
Project full title/acronym	Innovative local public-private-citizen partnership for energy governance /Vilawatt
Funding Programme	UIA (2016 - 2019)
Project website	https://uia-initiative.eu/en/uia-cities/viladecans
Project status (ongoing / completed)	Completed (1/11/2016 to 31/10/2019)
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	VILAWATT project tried to create an innovative Public-Private-Citizen organizational structure (PPCP), for energy governance at local level (in the city of Viladecans, Catalonia).
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	The innovative solution of PPCP tried to integrate 4 key tools for the energy transition: (ONE-LEVEL-GOVERNANCE) -Local energy operator (to supply and produce RES) -Local energy savings service operator (including innovative Energy Savings Contracting Model to capitalize energy savings) -Local energy investments operator (ESCO for deep energy renovation investments) -Local energy savings-based currency.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	A mindset change in the local population, through enhanced knowledge and capacities related to energy transition and renovation of buildings. A new PPCP organization for energy governance that will empower and engage citizens, local administration and public sector for the energy transition. A deep renovation of 60 dwellings, supported by a participative scheme, and given high visibility. Still being finished after project ending!
References	Project description:

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	https://uia-initiative.eu/sites/default/files/2016-12/Viladecans%20-%20MEDIA%20-%20PPT%20presentation.pdf
No. of Project	11
Project full title/acronym	C-TRACK 50
Funding Programme	Horizon 2020
Project website	https://www.c-track50.eu
Project status (ongoing / completed)	Completed
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	<p>C-Track 50 focused on the multi-level governance models adopted in the 11 countries (AT, DE, ES, FR, EL, HR, HU, LV, PL, PT, RO) and drew conclusions and recommendations on implementing and tailoring collaboration processes. The results are published in the report on existing multi-level governance (see links below).</p> <p>An analysis of the existing energy planning processes within 11 countries focusing on national target setting procedures and synopsis of the process for formulation national energy and climate policy plans including the role of local and regional governments was performed and summarized in a report (see link below).</p> <p>Achieving multi-level governance in energy and climate planning was one of the main goals of C-Track50. More specifically, the project linked up EU, national, regional and local authorities to establish multi-level cooperation and ensure synergies when developing and implementing sustainable energy and climate policy plans. Collaboration was sought through roundtables and bilateral discussions at all levels, whilst national and regional stakeholders had the opportunity to exchange experiences at a European level. This collaboration facilitated integrated planning and linked up national energy and climate priorities and efforts with regional and local policies and actions. As such, local and regional plans were aligned with National Energy Efficiency Action Plans (NEEAPs), National Renewable Energy Action Plans (NREAPs) and other key national plans prepared by Member States. Moreover, the collaboration of financial institutions and market actors facilitated the funding of selected actions.</p> <p>Additionally, capacity building activities covered knowledge gaps and needs at a regional and local level, so that local and regional</p>

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	<p>authorities are empowered to develop integrated energy and climate policy plans for 2050, but also to secure funding for the implementation of selected actions. The capacity building activities also enabled regional authorities and energy agencies to better support local authorities in setting long-term targets and developing actions to achieve these, removing a significant barrier that is the lack of technical expertise. Overall, regional and local authorities developed multidisciplinary and technical skills, required for the development and financing of sustainable energy and climate actions.</p>
<p>Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities</p>	<p><u>Methodology #1</u></p> <p>C-Track 50 has gathered a number of inspiring multi-level governance examples and best practices across 11 EU countries and mapped the status quo of the policy planning processes at the national level to better understand the difficulties and challenges these may cause at the local level. These examples and best practices were collected via a questionnaire circulated among the national partners. The identified best practices cover a wide area of decarbonisation sectors - building retrofitting, energy plans, territorial development, energy efficiency, mobility- and include collaboration models in all levels of governance. Procedures applicable at each country level were thoroughly reviewed and discussed, during these national roundtables. Relevant recommendations on improving national priorities between national, regional and local authorities, especially in sight of the ambitious targets set on energy and climate policy planning at the EU level, have been produced and added to the final report as recommendations.</p> <p><u>Methodology #2</u></p> <p>The "Guidebook for achieving Carbon Neutrality by 2050" was developed as part of the H2020 project C-Track 50 and describes the key steps in the planning process, along with important considerations in each step. It also presents best practices to inspire cities and regions and help them better design actions to take forward in the decarbonisation process.</p> <p><u>Digital platform</u></p> <p>The C-Track 50 Knowledge Repository (see References for link) is a dissemination portal including significant material that can support local and regional policy planning processes, as well as provide access to citizens to information regarding the implementation of energy improvement actions. To this end, EU strategic documents, national/regional energy and climate plans, legislative acts, as well as tools such as energy calculators for residences, and links to registries of certified technicians that can implement energy efficiency and renewable energy interventions have been included. The platform has been populated both with documents by partners for their respective countries and with EU documents and it is accessible in 10 languages, besides English.</p>
<p>Implementation status</p>	<p>C-Track 50 employed an innovative approach in empowering regional/local authorities, by building their capacity and addressing</p>

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(progress; barriers; delays)	<p>barriers in energy planning, as well as enabling them to actively contribute to the EU’s long term energy policy targets, by introducing the carbon neutrality concept at regional/local level, ensuring at the same time multi governance collaboration at all levels to facilitate the planning process.</p> <p>In conclusion, C-Track 50 applied this innovative approach and engaged national and sub-national authorities in eleven (11) countries, and as a result it:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitated the development and implementation of one hundred and seven (107) integrated sustainable energy and climate resilient plans at a local level, • Provided recommendations/facilitated the development of eleven (11) integrated sustainable energy and climate resilient plans at a regional level and, • Provided recommendations for establishing new/revising existing energy and climate policies at a national level, in line with the carbon neutrality target by 2050.
References	<p>Existing Multi-level Governance Models in 11 EU Countries: https://www.c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/inline-images/Briefing_paper_final.pdf</p> <p>Putting Regions on Track for Carbon Neutrality by 2050 - Final Publishable Report - November 2021 https://c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/2021/Final%20Publishable%20Report%20%282%29.pdf</p> <p>Energy Planning Process Report in 11 EU Countries: https://www.c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/inline-images/View%20Report.pdf</p> <p>Guidebook for achieving Carbon Neutrality by 2050 https://c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/2021-06/Guidebook_for_Achieving_Carbon_Neutrality_by_2050.pdf</p> <p>Recommendations on national energy priorities in the eleven participating countries https://www.c-track50.eu/sites/default/files/inline-images/C-Track50_Del_D2_5.pdf</p> <p>C-Track 50 Knowledge Repository: https://www.c-track50.eu/knowledge-repository</p>

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No. of Project	12
Project full title/acronym	COOPENERGY
Funding Programme	Intelligent Energy Europe
Project website	https://fedarene.org/project/coopenergy/
Project status (ongoing / completed)	Completed
Introduced governance structure / figure for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	-
Introduced tool / methodology / digital platform for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	COOPENERGY fostered a more collaborative approach between regional and local public authorities for more cohesion in the design and implementation of their respective sustainable energy action plans. COOPENERGY developed a database of 60 best practice examples of multi-level governance across Europe as well as a guidebook with a step-by-step approach on how to implement multi-level governance.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	
References	Coopenergy - A guide to Multi-level Governance for local and regional public authorities

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	https://fedarene.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/151202-FINAL-Coopenergy-Guidebook.pdf COOPENERGY - 60 best practices on MLG collaboration for sustainable energy planning: https://fedarene.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/04/Final-60-BPs-compressed.pdf
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No. of Project	13
Project full title/ acronym	DATA4ACTION
Funding Programme	Intelligent Energy Europe
Project website	https://fedarene.org/project/data4action/
Project status (<i>ongoing / completed</i>)	Completed
Introduced governance structure / figure for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	Data4Action introduced regional observatories. These regional observatories are powerful tools for implementing efficient strategies at the local level. Most of the structures are governed by a local consortium gathering at least several public authorities and energy data suppliers. They are very often supported by public authorities and integrated within existing regional organizations such as energy agencies or public departments. The added value of this kind of structure is its high level of technical skills in data gathering and analysis, and in energy planning.
Introduced tool / methodology / digital platform for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	Observatories of the Data4action all have tools to inform local and regional energy transition policies (data collection, data monitoring, data visualisation and exchanges with local authorities) and monitor their implementation on their territories.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	Within the Data4Action project, 4 Regional Energy Observatories: Oreges Rhône Alpes (FR), Energieluppen of Norrbotten (SE), Ligurian Energy and Environment Observatory (IT) & Climate Observatory Nord-Pas de Calais (FR) have supported the creation of 7 new ones in Alba

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	(RO), Carlow Kilkenny (IE), Torino (IT), Plovdiv (BG), Zlin (CZ), Kent (UK) and Greece.
References	<p>Data4Action - Energy data sharing for sustainable energy planning: https://fedarene.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/D4A_final-publishable-report.pdf</p> <p>Data4Action - Policy recommendations on improving energy data sharing for effective energy planning at sub-national levels: https://fedarene.org/publication/policy-recommendations-on-improving-energy-data-sharing-for-effective-energy-planning-at-sub-national-levels/</p> <p>Data4Action - Data Access Guidebook for SEAPs: https://fedarene.org/publication/data4action-data-access-guidebook-for-seaps/</p> <p>Data4Action - Project Leaflet: https://fedarene.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/valide-16-04-2017D4A-6.2_Leaflet_EU.pdf</p>

No. of Project	14
Project full title/ acronym	PELAGOS
Funding Programme	Interreg MED 2014-2020
Project website	https://pelagos.interreg-med.eu/
Project status (ongoing / completed)	Completed
Introduced governance structure / figure for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	<p>PELAGOS aims to establish a permanent Cluster of national HUBs in the Blue Energy (BE) sector, where technical experiences are shared. Permanent communication among actors is a crucial asset for the evolution and advancement of the project and its effective contribution to the Blue Growth of Mediterranean coastal, insular and offshore regions.</p> <p>The specific scope of PELAGOS is to facilitate the deployment of targeted technological solutions and products that are tailored to the characteristics of the Mediterranean environment.</p>

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Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	Blue Energy Cluster Building Methodology (see link in references below)
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	The project ended in 2019. Barriers regarding the development of innovation in the Blue Energy sector where presented in the deliverables included in references below.
References	Blue Energy Cluster Building Methodology. Diagnostic study of the Mediterranean marine energy resources potential. Existing Policy and regulatory status on MED Blue Energy development. Deployment potential assessment of Blue Energy Technologies for MED key Maritime industries.

No. of Project	15
Project full title/ acronym	Heraklion 2030 “Climate-Neutral & Smart City”
Funding Programme	Horizon Europe (2021-2027)
Project website	https://mission100.heraklion.gr/
Project status (<i>ongoing / completed</i>)	Ongoing
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council,	Participation in this EU Mission for climate neutral and smart cities by 2030 will ensure that these cities act as experimentation and innovation hubs to put all European cities in a position to become climate-neutral by 2050. With its participation, the Municipality of Heraklion prepared a web-platform for public consultation on the different measures identified within the Municipal Strategy for climate neutrality and aspires to meet the challenges arising from the transition by organizing with

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committee, designated individual etc.)	<p>reliability, transparency and inclusiveness a process of continuous and effective consultation with the local community.</p> <p>At least 2.000 residences will be influenced by the Municipality's annual initiative of conducting energy inspections and consultations (the so-called "participative energy transition" initiative) to proceed to at least minor (e.g. behavioural) actions. The purpose of the action is to achieve citizens behavioural shift towards rational use of energy in their houses.</p>
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	<p>With their participation in this eu initiative, 100 EU cities are expected to have access to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tailor-made advice and assistance from the Mission Platform (managed by the NetZeroCities consortium); • Unlocking additional funding and financing opportunities through a Mission label; • Research & innovation funding opportunities for cities to join large innovation actions, pilot projects and demonstrations (total budget from Horizon Europe for 2021-2023 is €360 million); • Support through a national coordination network Networking opportunities, learning and exchange of experiences among cities; • Support with involving citizens in decision-making High visibility - raised political profile and attractiveness for investment and skilled workers.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p>Heraklion Municipality was not included in the 10 EU cities selected in April 2022 but in light of the overwhelming interest from 377 cities to join the mission, the Commission is putting in place support for cities that were not selected, including support through the Mission Platform and funding opportunities under the Cities Mission Work Programme of Horizon Europe.</p>
References	<p>https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_22_2591</p> <p>https://www.intelligentcitieschallenge.eu/cities/heraklion</p>

No. of Project	16
Project full title/ acronym	ECOROUTS
Funding Programme	Interreg Greece-Cyprus 2014-2020
Project website	https://mission100.heraklion.gr/

Project status (<i>ongoing / completed</i>)	Completed (2021).
Introduced governance structure / figure for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	The aim of the ECOROUTS project was to reduce CO ₂ emissions and other harmful gases for both human health and the environment and to promote actions that reduce environmental risks from urban transport. Particular objectives are to create incentives for the use of environmentally friendly urban transport, to enhance access to more user-friendly information services in order to increase the accessibility and attractiveness of areas and to create the right conditions for the adoption of electrification in the area of the project as well as beyond it.
Introduced tool / methodology / digital platform for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	<p>An innovative element was the introduction of zero-pollutant vehicles that will be used by both the local population and visitors as well as by people with disabilities. The creation of a system within urban areas with remarkable tourist traffic, which are characterized by high levels of air pollution such as the project area, will have the effect of rebuilding a quality living standard for residents and visitors in a healthy and clean environment.</p> <p>Promotion of means and modes of transport (electric vehicles) within the historical center of Municipalities participating in the project with zero environmental footprint and less noise than conventional.</p> <p>In particular, the Municipality of Heraklion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Procured 2 electric buses of small size and pilot operation on two routes in the historical center; - Prepared a Study of routes to historic sites setting up bus stops oriented towards the emergence of cultural and historical monuments; - Developed a web-based application that allows real-time information, whether via the Internet or via mobile phones, to allow actual arrivals and departures to be based on a GPS system and real-time information to be available about the closest stops and the total route of the electric buses, as well as a telematics system where, via electronic signs located at each stop - historic site, the visitor is informed about the arrival of the bus and the historical data concerning the location.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	-
References	https://ecorouts-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Project-ECOROUTS_English.pdf

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	https://flashnews.gr/post/459199/hrakleio-prasines-kai-prosbasimes-diadromes-gia-oloys/
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No. of Project	17
Project full title/ acronym	Telemetry & remote-control of leaks in new water networks, expanding automation to new local stations and upgrading local automation control stations (SCADA)
Funding Programme	Greece National Operational program for Transport Infrastructure, Environment and Sustainable Development) of the NSRF 2014-2020
Project website	https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/EN/atlas/programmes/2014-2020/greece/2014gr16m1op001
<p>ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΙΑΚΟ ΠΡΟΓΡΑΜΜΑ Υποδομές Μεταφορών, Περιβάλλον και Αειφόρος Ανάπτυξη</p>	
Project status (ongoing / completed)	Ongoing
Introduced governance structure / figure for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	This particular measure of the National Operational Program was to ensure the rational management of the country's water resources as well as to improve the quality and industry of the water stock while reducing leaks. An open call to all Municipalities and their Municipal sewage services was released in 2017 and six (6) Municipalities of Crete (Rethymno, Maleviziou, Chania, Hersonissos, Minoa Pediadas, Agios Nikolaos) were successfully evaluated in 2018 to upgrade their water systems with the installation of telemetry, automation and leak control systems . The data will be managed remotely from the existing and new Local Water Control Stations for the overall management of the water distribution in each Municipality.
Introduced tool / methodology / digital platform for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET	Expanding automation to new local stations and upgrading local automation control stations (SCADA). The reduction of water leakages is expected to have a positive impact in water and energy saving since in most cases, the operation of water

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projects by public authorities	pumps is the most energy consuming infrastructure in all Greek Municipalities.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	Under implementation. Delays in releasing public tenders for the procurement of relevant equipment are due to bureaucracy, considering that the cost for each project is over 1mil euros.
References	https://government.gov.gr/88-6-ekat-evro-stous-ota-gia-tin-anavathmisi-ton-diktion-idrefsis-ke-ton-periorismo-ton-diarroon/
No. of Project	18
Project full title/ acronym	Actions of Energy Upgrading and Energy Saving (EE) and Utilization of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) in Sports Facilities
Funding Programme	Greek National Operational Program "Transport Infrastructure, Environment and Sustainable Development" and Regional Operational Program of Crete 2014-2020
Project website	http://www.rethymno.gr
Project status (ongoing / completed)	Ongoing
Introduced governance structure / figure for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	<p>Many Cretan municipalities (i.e. Heraklion, Ierapetra) were successfully evaluated under the framework of the National Operational Programme in order to upgrade the energy efficiency of Sports Facilities (Pancretan Stadium in Heraklion and Gym named Markos Foniadakis in Ierapetra).</p> <p>Similarly, fifteen (15) new projects, related to energy savings in public buildings with a total budget of 12 million euros, are included in the Regional Operational Program "CRETE 2014-2020".</p> <p>These projects upgrade energy public buildings, in order to achieve the goals set in the National Action Plan for Energy Efficiency. The energy upgrade projects concern the Indoor Gym of Tavronitis, the City Hall of Platania and, in Rethymno, the building of the Regional Unit, the City Hall and the 1st High School of the city. Also, the Gymnasiums of Platania and Souda, the Gymnasiums - Lyceums of Alikianos and Agia Varvara, the school complexes of Amberia and Koumbe of Chania, the 2nd Primary School of Archanes and the Gymnasium - EPAL of Kantanos will be upgraded in energy.</p>

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	The projects will be implemented by the Region of Crete and the involved Municipalities of the island.
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	Assignment of expertise for energy upgrade projects, from which a methodology of project categorization was defined and templates with Technical Specifications were prepared that cover all potential systems (as described in page 150 of the annual report included in References below).
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	Ongoing. Delays associated to public procurement processes. See page 150 of the annual report included in References below, for barriers and delays.
References	Annual implementation report: https://ymeperaa.gr/images/Implementation_report_2014GR16M1OPO1_2020_0_el.pdf Indicative study for the sports centre in Chania Municipality: https://www.chania.gr/files/55/44814/06_tehniki_ekthesi_naytathliti_koy_soydas_signed.pdf?rnd=1637663502 Programme information

No. of Project	19
Project full title/ acronym	Junior Energy Inspectors in Action in the Municipality of Hersonissos
Funding Programme	Implemented under the framework of the 1 st Grade curriculum in Greek schools for the elaboration of a scientific project.
Project website	http://www.hersonisos.gr
Project status (ongoing / completed)	Completed
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for	Pupils played the role of the “ Energy Inspector ”, by measuring the total surface of the walls and open spaces of their school building, the Town Hall and their library building. Energy consumption was

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coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	calculated as well as carbon dioxide emissions, according to standards set out by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. During the project's implementation, pupils studied, with the aid of a voluntary Energy Inspector, the Greek legislative framework on energy and the recent rules on buildings' energy efficiency.
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	Inclusion of secondary schools and pupils in the process of calculating energy consumption. The need for this project came up due to the information gap that pupils and young people in general, have on the irreversible effects of human activity on climate change. The project aimed at studying the effects of climate change and in particular the relation of energy consumption with increment of carbon dioxide emissions. In addition, students scrutinized ways of reducing energy consumption and ways of introducing renewable energy resources.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	Completed.
References	https://www.hersonisos.gr/en/municipal/schoollproject1/schoolproject.html https://kede.gr/chersonisos-oi-energeiakoi-epitheorites-junior-analamvanoun-kai-pali-drasi/

No. of Project	20
Project full title/ acronym	INTEgrated sustainable enERgy ACTions and projects in Crete (INTERACT in Crete)
Funding Programme	ELENA (European Local ENergy Assistance) - European Investment Bank ELENA provides technical assistance for energy efficiency and renewable energy investments targeting buildings and innovative urban transport.
Project website	https://www.eib.org/attachments/documents/119-project-factsheet-interact-in-crete.pdf

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 The European Investment Bank
ELENA – European Local ENergy Assistance

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Project status (<i>ongoing / completed</i>)	Ongoing
Introduced governance structure / figure for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	<p>A Memorandum of Understanding was signed among the Region of Crete and 13 Cretan municipalities describing responsibilities of each involved stakeholder within the INTERACT in CRETE project in order to proceed in the energy upgrading of all relevant installations (municipal public lighting, hospitals and health centres). The interventions for the energy upgrade of public lighting are expected to have an overall reduction by 69% in energy consumption from the sector.</p> <p>The ultimate goal of ELENA project is the creation of energy communities for net metering, virtual net-metering and the installation of integrated photovoltaic panels.</p>
Introduced tool / methodology / digital platform for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	<p>The project officially started on 16/12/2020 with the signature of the contract between the Region of Crete and the European Investment Bank. Due to COVID19 there have been some delays in its progress but recently the procurement of the relevant technical studies have been released and hopefully it will end on time.</p> <p>In March 2022 the Region of Crete released a call for the public procurement of maturation studies for the Energy Upgrade - Automation of the Street Lighting System in the Urban Lighting System of 8 Municipalities of the Region of Crete (Archanon-Asterousion, Phaistou, Mylopotamou, Apokorona, Amariou, Heraklion, Hersonissos).</p> <p>In April 2022 the Region of Crete released a call for the public procurement of maturation studies for the Energy Upgrading of Hospitals, Health Centers and Other Public Buildings in the Region of Crete.</p> <p>The main barriers for energy upgrade of public buildings in Greece / Crete always include: out of date / absence of building permits and construction licenses / structural tests.</p>
References	https://www.eib.org/en/products/advising/elena/index.htm

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Project full title/ acronym	STEPPING
Funding Programme	Interreg MED 2014-2020
Project website	https://stepping.interreg-med.eu/
Project status (<i>ongoing / completed</i>)	<p>STEPPING project was implemented from January 2016 and was completed in October 2019.</p> <p>STEPPING PLUS is an On-going project that started in March 2021.</p>
Introduced <i>governance structure / figure</i> for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	-
Introduced <i>tool / methodology / digital platform</i> for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	<p>Within the STEPPING project a common methodology was identified. More than 70 public authorities were engaged thanks to local events and a technical assistance service provided, for the preparation of energy efficiency investments. For the purpose, 22 Formal Agreements were signed. Small municipalities of a specific area were pooled together to develop Joint Investment Plans (economy of scale plus critical mass for the EPC market requirements) and, in some cases, to launch the EPC tender. After the selection of 170 suitable buildings an energy audit campaign was carried on, back to back with training activity in each of the regions involved. The common working approach, schemes and tools developed by the project partners allowed the drafting of 16 Investment Plans, tailored to the different framework conditions of the territories. Their implementation would bring to a total investment of about 18,5 M€ with an energy saving of 7 GWh/year and about 2000 t of CO₂/year avoided emission. Thanks to a wide involvement of policy makers and stakeholders STEPPING released the “EPC Policy recommendations” and all the experience gained during the project implementation, together with an analysis of the specificity of the MED Area, was resumed in the EPC MED Guidelines. This document provides extremely useful advises to all the subjects interested in replicating and improving the STEPPING lessons learnt. Despite the existence of some technical issues (i.e. the climatic specificity of the MED Area, the level of maturity of the market, the financial framework conditions) and several political and</p>

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	administrative bottlenecks, the main goals of the project were achieved even more than expected.
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	Despite the existence of some technical issues (i.e. the climatic specificity of the MED Area, the level of maturity of the market, the financial framework conditions) and several political and administrative bottlenecks, the main goals of the project were achieved to a degree even higher than expected.
References	One of the key deliverables of STEPPING is the MED EPC Guidelines aiming to provide step-by-step guidance for the energy retrofitting of public buildings in the MED area through the use of Energy Performance Contracts, taking into consideration the intrinsic characteristics of the region: https://aegean-energy.gr/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/med-guidelines.pdf

6 Summary of legal and policy framework

The review of the legal and policy framework in the pilot territories identified **fourty-four (44) key Laws and policy documents / plans** relevant to energy transition:

- 18 applicable at national level;
- 10 applicable at regional level;
- 16 applicable at local level.

The identified documents are summarised below:

<i>GREECE / Crete Region</i>
1. Law 4122/2013 on the Energy Efficiency of Buildings - (transposition of recast EPBD 2010/31/EU)
2. Law 4342/2015 on Energy Efficiency (transposition of EED 2012/27/EU)
3. Law 4685/2020 (transposition of 2018/844/EU - amending 2010/31/EU and 2012/27/EU)
4. Law 4513/2018 on Energy Communities
5. Law 4710/2020 on the Promotion of e-mobility - (transposition of 2019/1161/EU)
6. Law 4843/2021 (transposition of 2018/2002/EU -amending 2012/27/EU, adapting to the provisions of 2018/1999/EU on the Governance of the EU and Climate Action, and to provisions of 2019/826/EU)
7. National Energy and Climate Plan (2019)
8. Long-term strategy for the renovation of the public and private building stock and its transformation into high energy efficiency low carbon building stock by 2050
9. 16 SEAPs / SECAPs of Municipalities in Crete (CoM)
10. Regional Plan for the Adaptation to Climate Change of the Region of Crete
11. 6 Sustainable Mobility Action Plans of Municipalities of Crete

<i>SPAIN / Catalonia / Girona Region</i>
1. Royal Decree 235/2013, approving the basic procedure for the certification of the energy performance of buildings (transposition of recast EPBD 2010/31/EU)
2. Royal Decree 56/2016, on energy efficiency, as regards energy audits, accreditation of energy service providers and auditors, and promotion of the efficiency of energy supply (transposition of EED 2012/27/EU)
3. Royal Decree 732/2019, amending the Spanish Technical Building Code (transposition of 2018/844/EU - amending recast EPBD 2010/31/EU and 2012/27/EU)
4. Royal Decree 244/2019, on self-consumption of electric energy

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5. Royal Decree-law 23/2020, adopting energy and other measures for economic recovery
6. Law 16/2017, of climate change

CZECH Republic / Zlín Region
1. Decree No. 264/2020 Coll., on the energy performance of buildings (transposition of the recast EPBD 2010/31/EU, 2012/27/EU and 2018/844/EU)
2. Legislation on Energy Communities (in development, likely to be incorporated into the Law No. 458/2000 Coll., Energy Act)
3. Government Resolution No. 685 on the introduction of the Rules for the Support of Low-Emission Vehicles through Public Procurement and Public Passenger Transport Services (transposition of 2019/1161/EU)
4. 3 Laws for the implementation of 2018/2002/EU
5. The Czech Republic 's National Energy and Climate Plan
6. The Energy Action Plan and the Energy Efficiency Financing Plan of the Zlín Region 2020 - 2024
7. Regional Action Plan for the Zlín Region

The following table summarises the current status of legal/policy framework related to energy transition governance, in the pilot territories:

Key laws & policies in ET Governance			
	CZECH Republic / Zlín Region	GREECE / Crete Region	SPAIN / Catalonia / Girona Region
EU Directives & Laws	(transposition)		
EPBD (Buildings Directive)	√	√	√
EED (Energy Efficiency Directive)	√	√	√
Low-emission Vehicles & e-Mobility (2019/1161/EU)	√	√	-
National/ Regional/ Local Laws, Regulations & Policies on:			
Energy Communities	√ <i>(in development)</i>	√	√
Climate Change	-	√	√
Energy & Climate Plan	√	√	√
Self-Consumption (electricity)	-	√	√
Regional Energy Action Plan	√	-	-
Energy efficiency Financing Plan	√	-	-

7 Summary of governance status in existing EU networks and initiatives

The review of existing EU networks and initiatives relevant to the ePLANET objectives identified **ten (10) EU-wide networks and initiatives**, that one or more of the ePLANET partners participate in, which introduce governance structures and tools that could be useful for ePLANET as they could be linked to the new governance structures and tools to be proposed at the next stages of the project.

The identified networks and respective **governance structures / tools** are summarised below:

<i>Network / initiative</i>	<i>Governance structures/figures for coordinating and monitoring ET plans and actions</i>	<i>Tools/ methodologies/ digital platforms for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects</i>
<p>10,948 Signatories (54 countries)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Signatories ❖ Coordinators ❖ Supporters ❖ CoM Europe Office ❖ EC (DG ENER and DG CLIMA) and JRC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Structure for Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP) and related guidance ❖ Digital platform for reporting/monitoring: MyCovenant Reporting Corner - templates to report and monitor the data of local action plans. ❖ Offline simplified SECAP excel template
<p>11,754 cities (from 6 continents -142 countries)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Global CoM Board ❖ Strategic Advisory Committee (SAC) to the Board (<i>European / Global / Regional Networks & Partners</i>) ❖ Funders Group ❖ Global Secretariat ❖ Regional / National Covenants ❖ Regional / National Secretariats ❖ Tailored governance structures (established through each Regional/National 	<p>Global CoM's Common Reporting Framework - recognising two official platforms for reporting on climate and energy measures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ MyCovenant Platform ❖ CDP-ICLEI Unified Reporting System: Online questionnaire annually updated - 15 sections with topics such as climate adaptation and mitigation actions, GHG emissions inventory, emissions reduction targets, energy efficiency and renewable energy targets, food systems,

	Covenant e.g. coordination group, advisory committee, steering group/committee, etc.)	buildings, waste management and water security.
<p>358 local & regional energy agencies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ It places Energy Agencies at the forefront of energy investments in Europe, considered in a unique position to support ET in their regions and cities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Online “Resources” database, with sections ‘Guidelines/ Methodology’, ‘Tools’, ‘Platforms’, and selection between a range of topics related to energy transition (buildings, transport, renewables etc.)
<p>76 islands, 29 with published Clean Energy Transition Agendas / Plans</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Clean energy for EU islands secretariat: central platform for the clean ET of more than 2,200 inhabited European islands (best practices, policy/ regulatory issues, dedicated advice for capacity building and clean energy transitioning). ❖ Memorandum of Understanding between the EC and 14 EU countries with island populations to establish a long-term framework for cooperation to advance ET ❖ Forums, regularly organised in combination with technical fairs, provide EU islands and other EU initiatives the opportunity to share best practices and show innovative projects in the areas of RES, EE and innovation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Clean Energy Transition Agenda (CETA) template (docx). Strategic roadmap for the local community transition process towards clean energy. ❖ Islands Transition Handbook - detailed guidance on how to develop a CETA ❖ Self-assessment Tool (excel): It helps islands to evaluate the current status of their clean energy transition according to eight indicators (e.g. energy vision, stakeholders’ commitment, project opportunities etc.)

<p>European Network of GhG Emissions and Energy Watch</p> <p>10 partners (7 energy agencies)</p> <p>20 Regional Energy and GhG Emissions observatories</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Regional Energy and GhG Emissions observatories provide data and knowledge about the region related to climate change, covering a variety of topics e.g. energy, emissions, air quality, social, economic or environmental effects. ❖ Most of them are governed by a local consortium gathering at least several public authorities and energy data suppliers. They are very often supported by public authorities and integrated within existing regional organizations such as energy agencies or public department. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ TerriSTORY: Online tool to support territories in following and achieving their energy and climate objectives (not developed by ENERGee Watch but by one of its partners, and promoted through a project learning course).
<p>56 members of which 52 Greek island Municipalities, the Regions of North Aegean, South Aegean, Ionian Islands and the Regional Union of Municipalities of the Ionian Islands.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Supporting, empowering local government, raising awareness and actively involving citizens in the implementation of projects with a positive impact for local development in areas such as: green energy, environment, sustainable tourism, circular economy, sustainable mobility, education and employment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Integrated management of natural resources and infrastructures, uptake of sustainable tourism and enhanced interdependence of the primary, secondary and tertiary sectors.
<p>20 members, from countries:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Greening the Islands Observatory ❖ Greening the Islands App: The online islands' scientific community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ The Greening the Islands Observatory aggregates key stakeholders to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Match island needs and innovative sustainable solutions - Produce reports & studies to address strategies and policies

<p>TANZANIA, GREECE, MALDIVES, ITALY, MALTA, GERMANY, TUNISIA, SPAIN, ESTONIA, CROATIA, UNITED KINGDOM, CAPE VERT.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Greening the Islands Awards Regulation 2021 ❖ Greening the Islands Academy ❖ Disseminating knowledge and best practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Originate projects, business models and financing opportunities - Promote the cooperation between governments and corporates
<p>10 companies-members of the Cluster, which employ more than 140 people.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Small Energy Cluster for renewable energies and environmental technologies. It provides services for green-tech companies in the field of renewable energy and energy efficiency technologies 	<p>CRETAN ENERGY CLUSTER aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The organized promotion of RES systems; - The emergence of our natural energy resources; - Informing and educating our members about new markets; - The communication with local educational institutions and public bodies; - Organized contact with suppliers.
<p>42 public bodies 12 private bodies 26 Community Support Organisations</p> <p>From 12 countries: Croatia, Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Malta, Netherlands</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ 33 island representatives came together in the European Parliament to sign on behalf of over 200 islands the Smart islands Declaration, cornerstone document of the Initiative. ❖ The Smart Islands Initiative is acknowledged as a meaningful vehicle for islands' transition to a low-carbon, smart and sustainable future. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ A multilevel governance project was produced titled "SMILEGOV". ❖ Similar to this initiative with several relevant deliverables is also the Horizon2020 project titled "SMart ISLand Energy systems" ("SMILE"), with a library containing policy recommendations for energy planning in island areas.
<p>64 insular communities have signed the Pact of Islands, from 9 countries: UK, Portugal, Cyprus, Greece, Sweden, Spain, Malta, Italy, Denmark</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ The Pact of Islands is a political initiative of European island municipalities and regions aiming at reducing island carbon dioxide emissions by 20% by 2020. The Pact was developed in line with the Covenant of Mayors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ A number of software tools and methodologies to help new signatories develop their own energy models, ISEAPs and Bankable Projects.

8 Summary of governance status in the 3 pilot territories

The review of the existing governance status in the 3 pilot territories of the project (Region of Crete-Greece, Province of Girona-Region of Catalonia-Spain, Zlín Region -Czech Republic), identified the existing governance structures and tools deployed in each of these territories to monitor and coordinate energy transition plans and actions at different governance levels, as well as the lack of them and barriers met in some cases, so the outcomes can feed the forthcoming stages of the project whereby new governance structures and tools will be proposed by ePLANET to improve coordination in multi-level governance.

The existing **governance structures / tools used in the pilot territories** are summarised below:

<i>Region of Crete (Greece)</i>	
<i>Governance structures/ figures for coordinating and monitoring ET plans and actions</i>	<i>Tools/ methodologies/ digital platforms for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects</i>
<p><i>Local (Municipal) level</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ CoM contact persons ❖ Energy managers of Municipal buildings <p><i>Regional level</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Regional Development Fund of Crete (RDFC) - Regional Energy Agency of Crete - Regional CoM Coordinator - supports the Region and the 24 Municipalities of Crete with energy advice and preparation of SEAPs. ❖ Energy managers of Regional buildings <p><i>National level</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Ministry of Environment & Energy ❖ CRES - National CoM Coordinator - supports local/regional authorities to prepare energy efficiency plans / SE(C)Aps ❖ Energy managers of Central government buildings 	<p><i>Methodology -Tool</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ 16 SEAPs/SECAPs of Municipalities in the Region of Crete, in the framework of the CoM ❖ Energy Efficiency Plan for Regional and Municipal buildings - Template by the Ministry of Environment and Energy ❖ National Energy and Climate Plan ❖ Regional Plan for the Adaptation to Climate Change ❖ 6 Sustainable Mobility Action Plans of Crete Municipalities <p><i>Digital platforms</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Use of CoM MyCovenant platform by the 16 Municipalities of Crete with SE(C)APs ❖ Energy reporting and monitoring tool for Energy Managers of public buildings (excel) by the Ministry of Environment and Energy

<i>Region of Girona (Catalonia, Spain)</i>	
<i>Governance structures/figures for coordinating and monitoring ET plans and actions</i>	<i>Tools/ methodologies/ digital platforms for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects</i>
<p><i>Municipal and Regional level</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ The Mayor is the formal signatory of the Covenant, and there are also designated CoM contact persons from the Municipality, or in many cases, an Energy Transition Technician supporting the Municipality in anything related in energy through the Energy Transition Offices (OTE). ❖ Energy Transition Offices (OTE). Girona Region has 7 county councils and 3 of them have an Energy Transition Office, but in the future the idea is to implement an OTE to each county council. In each OTE there is an Energy Transition Technician to help municipalities with anything related in energy and the environment. <p><i>National level</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ The Ministry for the ecological transition and demographic challenge is the responsible Government authority in Spain for all issues related to energy policy and energy transition and at the level of the autonomous community of Catalonia the authorized entity is ICAEN ❖ Diputació de Girona is the National CoM coordinator in Girona, with institutional role to provide technical support to Municipalities authorities to prepare energy efficiency plans and actions. 	<p><i>Methodology -Tool</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ 201 Sustainable Energy (and Climate) Action Plans (SECAPs) of Municipalities in the Region of Girona, in the framework of the Covenant of Mayors initiative (of total 210 Signatory Municipalities) ❖ European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), local section 2014-2020 <p>The ERDF OP provides for actions promoted by local authorities within the framework of priority axis 4, which aims to encourage the transition to a low-carbon economy in all sectors; and priority axis 6, which aims to conserve and protect the environment and promote resource efficiency.</p>

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Zlín Region (Czech Republic)	
<i>Governance structures/figures for coordinating and monitoring ET plans and actions</i>	<i>Tools/ methodologies/ digital platforms for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects</i>
<p><i>Municipal and Regional level</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Solid and well-established ET vertical governance: ET strategy mainly defined by EAZK, and later adopted by the Region. Local authorities implement the ET rather through planning particular projects and implementation, hardly any of them have a real SEAP. ❖ 307 Municipalities in the Zlín Region - EAZK supports both the Region and the Municipalities to implement EE measures and increase RES share on energy supply in the Zlín Region. <p><i>National level</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Relevant stakeholders in financing the energy transition are at national level and they are mainly Ministries and their institutions (Ministry of Environment, State Environmental Fund, Ministry of Trade and Industry, Ministry of Regional Development). 	<p><i>Methodology -Tool</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Czech Republic National Energy and Climate Plan approved in 2019. In terms of more specific energy transition plans and measures, the issue is assessed from a regional perspective. ❖ Thanks to its nature EAZK has the accessibility to all reliable regional databases and documents on the potential of the Zlín Region. EAZK also participates in suggesting and implementation of strategic documents and policies of the Zlín Region in the field of energy, environment, and innovations.

9 Summary of best practices from past or ongoing projects

The review of past and ongoing EU and national projects relevant to the ePLANET objectives, with the participation of the consortium partners, has identified **twenty-one (21) relevant projects** from which best practices on multi-level governance can be identified:

- 16 transnational EU-funded projects (5 Horizon 2020 projects, 5 Interreg MED 2014-2020, 1 Interreg Europe, 1 Urban Innovative Actions -UIA, 2 Intelligent Energy Europe, 1 DG Energy, 1 ELENA-European Investment Bank);
- 5 National and/or Regional projects (1 co-funded by ERDF, Girona Provincial Council and involved Municipalities; 1 funded by Girona Provincial Council; 1 funded by the Greek NSRF; 1 funded by the Greek NSRF and the Regional Operational Programme of the Region of Crete; 1 local Municipal project).

In terms of the progress of implementation of the above projects,

- 13 are completed projects;
- 8 are ongoing projects.

The identified projects and respective **governance structures / tools** are summarised below:

<i>Project</i>	<i>Governance structures / figures for coordinating and monitoring ET plans and actions</i>	<i>Tools/ methodologies / digital platforms for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects</i>
<p>Integrated Management Support for Energy Efficiency in Mediterranean Public Buildings [IMPULSE]</p>	-	<p><i>Methodology</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ An integrated methodology (composed of a series of Excel-based tools) to support public authorities in the MED area in the development of oriented action plans for energy efficiency of public buildings at local level. <p><i>Digital platform</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Excel-based user-friendly platform for data-base creation of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for alternative retrofit scenarios for large samples of public buildings.

<p>SHared knowledge for Energy Renovation in buildings by Public Administrations [SHERPA]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ There was a proposal for setting up a formal governance structure to coordinate energy efficiency plans and actions for public buildings, coordinated by each SHERPA participating Region, with the participation of all respective Municipalities in the territory of the Region (e.g. for Region of Crete there was a proposal for such a Committee, to be coordinated by the Region). Eventually this governance structure was not formally set up. Perhaps it could be further explored for ePLANET. 	<p><i>Methodology - Tool</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Regional Energy Renovation of Buildings (ERB) Roadmaps were developed (incl. in the Region of Crete), in a coordinated multi-level governance approach coordinating regional and local strategies. <p><i>Digital platforms</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ SHERPA Shared Information System. Digital platform developed by CIMNE and used during the Testing phase to facilitate the participating partner Regions in collecting, comparing, benchmarking, information for the energy consumption and energy saving measures for their public buildings. The platform is no longer operational. ❖ SHERPA Capitalisation platform. An online platform developed by CRES as a “hub” of useful information available to all interested public authorities and stakeholders, operational beyond the end of SHERPA, including a searchable database of deliverables, best practices, tools, methodologies, from SHERPA and other relevant MED/EU projects and initiatives in the thematic of energy efficiency of buildings. Access to the platform is free.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Catalan pilot site main actors identified: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ~ 100 energy managers, responsible for the management of public buildings having 	<p><i>Tool</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ A Big Data TOOL with AI will allow to make decisions for a de-risking investments in ET projects (in buildings). Initially will contain

<p>Building Information aGGregation, harmonization and analytics platform [BIGG]</p>	<p>a weekly or monthly interaction with the energy management tool,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ~ 20 to 30 policy makers responsible for planning actions to improve energy performance of buildings with a monthly or bi annually interaction with the tool • ~ 10 public authorities on special interest on general building trends, having semi-annual or annual interaction with the tool. <p>❖ Greek pilot site different business cases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 17 large commercial office buildings in Athens managed through Energy Performance Contracting (EPC) and Maintenance Contract. • Focus on delivering flexibility services by managing appliances of residential and commercial consumers of electricity and natural gas, spread across various cities of Greece. 	<p>information from 4000 buildings of Generalitat of Catalonia.</p> <p><i>Digital platform</i></p> <p>❖ An Open source Big-Data reference Architecture for collection, processing and exchanging data from different sources.</p>
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<p>Energy Efficiency Performance-Tracking Platform for Benchmarking Savings and Investments in Buildings [EN-TRACK]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ EN-TRACK aims to enable a one-stop-shop platform to allow better decision making of investments in energy efficiency projects in buildings, for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial institutions - Building owners 	<p><i>Digital platform</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ The EN-TRACK platform will have several tools for different user levels: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>General Public:</i> Cross-sectional benchmarking tool to analyse: Energy Efficiency Measures; Building types • <i>Data providers:</i> Longitudinal benchmarking; Cross-sectional benchmarking
<p>De-Risking Energy Efficiency Platform [DEEP-EEFIG]</p>	<p>-</p>	<p><i>Digital platform</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ The EEFIG De-risking Energy Efficiency Platform (DEEP) is an open-source database for energy efficiency investments performance monitoring and benchmarking. It includes 15,000+ energy efficiency projects in buildings and industry from 30 data providers.
<p>Boilers, heat networks and facilities for chip production [Bebiomassgi]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ 22 Municipalities involved in the project. 7 biomass boilers were installed, 15 biomass heat networks were constructed and 2 forest biomass treatment facilities were built. 	<p><i>Methodology</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Each Municipality detailed the project carried out with the following information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Action • Description • Year of execution • Investment cost, broken down by contribution of each governance structure • CO₂ Savings • Energy savings • Renewable energy production • Percentage of energy savings

<p>Comunitats Locals d'Energia / Local Energy Communities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Girona Provincial Council is promoting this pioneering project in Spain, offering technical and financial support to local councils that wish to promote local energy communities. 	<p><i>Methodology</i></p> <p>The Girona Provincial Council has drawn up a guide to facilitate the implementation of local energy communities in the territory: Guide for the use of roofs and land for the local production of renewable energies.</p>
<p>Energy efficiency with Performance guarantees in the private and public sector [guarantEE]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Introduced a new figure, “EPC facilitator” as a key driver to foster EPC contracts. Main function: to give guidance and advice in those installations willing to do energy equipment renovation, to be done using the 	<p><i>Methodology</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ EPC contract model developed. <p><i>Tool</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ On-line tool for a pre-check of EPC availability.
<p>New finance for energy efficiency measures in Public Buildings [New Finance]</p>	<p>-</p>	<p><i>Methodology -Tool</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Based on EPC model contracting to implement energy efficiency projects and its finance. ❖ SHERPA Financing Tool adopted.
<p>Innovative local public-private-citizen partnership for energy governance [Vilawatt]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ The project tried to create an innovative Public-Private-Citizen organizational structure (PPCP), for energy governance at local level (in the city of Viladecans, Catalonia), that will empower and engage citizens, local administration and public sector for the energy transition. 	<p><i>Tools</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ The innovative solution of PPCP tried to integrate 4 key tools for the energy transition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Local energy operator (to supply and produce RES) -Local energy savings service operator (including innovative Energy Savings Contracting Model to capitalize energy savings) -Local energy investments operator (ESCO for deep energy renovation investments) -Local energy savings-based currency.

<p>C-TRACK 50</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ C-Track 50 focused on the multi-level governance models adopted in 11 countries and drew conclusions and recommendations on implementing and tailoring collaboration processes. The results are published in the report on existing multi-level governance. ❖ An analysis of the existing energy planning processes within 11 countries focusing on national target setting procedures and synopsis of the process for formulation national energy and climate policy plans including the role of local and regional governments was performed and summarized in a report. ❖ The project linked up EU, national, regional and local authorities to establish multi-level cooperation and ensure synergies. Local and regional plans were aligned with National Energy Efficiency Action Plans (NEEAPs), National Renewable Energy Action Plans (NREAPs) and other key national plans prepared by MS. 	<p><i>Methodology</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ The "Guidebook for achieving Carbon Neutrality by 2050" was developed as part of the project, which describes the key steps in the planning process, along with important considerations in each step. It also presents best practices to inspire cities and regions and help them better design actions to take forward in the decarbonisation process. <p><i>Digital platform</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ The C-Track 50 Knowledge Repository is a dissemination portal (accessible in 10 languages), including significant material that can support local and regional policy planning processes, as well as provide access to citizens to information regarding the implementation of energy improvement actions.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ COOPENERGY fostered a more collaborative approach between regional and local public authorities for more cohesion in the design and implementation of their respective sustainable energy action plans. 	<p><i>Methodology</i></p> <p>COOPENERGY developed a database of 60 best practice examples of multi-level governance across Europe as well as a guidebook with a step-by-step approach on how to implement multi-level governance.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Data4Action introduced Regional observatories, which are powerful tools for implementing efficient strategies at local level. Most of the structures are governed by a local consortium gathering at least several public authorities and energy data suppliers. They are very often supported by public authorities and integrated within existing regional organizations such as energy agencies or public departments. 	<p><i>Tools</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Observatories of the Data4action all have tools to inform local and regional energy transition policies (data collection, data monitoring, data visualisation and exchanges with local authorities) and monitor their implementation on their territories.
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10 Conclusions

The review that was undertaken as part of this report aimed to analyse requirements and provide an overview and better understanding of the current governance framework in the partners' territories, in terms of the current legal and policy framework for energy transition; existing structures and tools that are deployed by public authorities to coordinate and monitor energy transition plans and projects; best practices on multi-level governance from past or ongoing EU and national projects; barriers, lessons learnt, best practices in the implementation of the above, that could contribute to an improvement of the current vertical and horizontal governance processes for energy transition.

Some conclusions that can be drawn from the review are summarized below, including general conclusions applicable at project level, as well as some specific ones related to the participating partners' territories:

General conclusions

- The review of the legal and policy framework in the pilot territories identified forty-four (44) key Laws and policy documents / plans relevant to energy transition, the majority relating to Government Laws, regulations, policies related to energy efficiency, energy performance of buildings, energy communities, e-mobility etc. In the three pilot Regions there are also regional level policies and targets for energy planning and improvement of governance. In the Region of Crete energy transition actions are also integrated within the wider SE(C)APs developed by Municipalities in the context of the CoM.
- The majority of Municipalities in the Province of Girona and the Region of Crete are signatories of the CoM and have developed / are in the process of developing their SE(C)APs. In the Zlín Region there are no developed SE(C)APs yet by Municipalities.
- Energy communities and relevant implemented projects are quite developed in Spain / Province of Girona, less developed in Greece / Region of Crete and not so developed in the Czech Republic / Zlín Region.
- The review identified ten (10) EU networks and initiatives and twenty-one (21) past or ongoing EU and national projects, with the participation of one or more of the consortium partners, that are relevant to the ePLANET objectives and introduce governance structures and methodologies / tools / digital platforms that could be further exploited and linked to the new governance structures and tools to be proposed at the next stages of the ePLANET project. Indicative examples are listed below, and a more detailed analysis of structures and tools are included in sections 7-9 of this report:

Indicative examples of identified governance structures include:

- Regional level structure (e.g. Committee) for the coordination of energy transition with regional and Municipal authorities' participation;
- Energy managers of public buildings;
- CoM coordinators at local and regional level;
- One-stop shops for decision making in energy-efficiency projects;
- Energy communities, with the participation of local/regional councils and citizens;
- Energy Performance Contracting (EPC) facilitators;
- Public-Private-Citizen organisational structure (PPCP) for energy governance at local level;
- Regional Observatories.

Indicative examples of identified methodologies / tools / digital platforms include:

- Integrated methodology to support public authorities in the development of public buildings energy efficiency action plans at local level;
- Regional Energy Renovation of Buildings (ERB) Roadmaps, including Regional and Municipal buildings;
- Big Data Tool with AI allowing to make decisions for de-risking investments in ET projects in buildings;
- Open source Big-Data reference Architecture for collection, processing and exchanging data from different sources, with tools for different user levels (general public, data providers);
- Open-source database for energy efficiency investments performance monitoring and benchmarking;
- Guide to facilitate the implementation of local energy communities;
- Online tool for a pre-check of EPC availability;
- Database of best practice examples of multi-level governance across Europe.

Greece / Region of Crete

- It appears that in general there is limited multi-level governance coordination on energy transition between national, regional and local level in Greece, and the same applies to the pilot territory of Crete.
- The majority of the current legal and policy framework related to energy transition is at national level (Government Laws, national plans etc.), for which there have been delays in transposing the provisions of recent EU Directives (such as recast EPBD, EED etc.), thus delays in actually implementing these requirements by the public sector. There is also a Regional Plan for the Adaptation to Climate Change, recently approved.
- Even though there is a requirement for regional and national authorities to develop Energy Efficiency plans for public buildings under their administrative jurisdiction

that can be part of wider sustainable energy plans, only few local/regional authorities have already produced such plans.

- ~69% of the Municipalities in Greece (229 of total 332) are Signatories of the CoM and 147 of them (~45%) have already submitted SE(C)APs.
- Even though there is a requirement for public authorities to appoint designated Energy Managers for their public buildings to monitor the energy consumption of public buildings in their responsibility, set improvement targets, and regularly report to the Ministry of Environment and Energy using a provided Excel-based tool, there have been delays by public authorities in appointing these designated persons, and since appointed, only some of them have been undertaking the process of regular collection, monitoring and reporting. Information from the Excel-tools is not collected centrally by each Region, for all Regional and Municipal buildings.
- Despite an e-platform for energy managers having been announced by the Ministry of Environment & Energy, it has not yet been released; hence there is lack of automatic central coordination of the collected information.
- Even though the legal framework has been put in force in the recent years to support energy communities, progress has been slow in creating them due to lack of know-how and lack of awareness of both public authorities and citizens.
- More specifically in the pilot territory of the Region of Crete, 20 Municipalities are signatories of the CoM, 16 of which have already prepared and submitted a SE(C)AP, however only 4 of them are in the phase of monitoring their SEAP and have submitted monitoring / progress reports.
- Information on the actual data uploaded by Municipalities on the MyCovenant platform or the offline Excel files used, is not publicly available and is not available to CRES/RDFC. Only summary information and KPIs for each SE(C)AP is publicly available from the CoM website. Contact with each Municipality would be required in order to obtain detailed information, and in many cases it is not easily found, as SE(C)APs may have been prepared by external consultants, without strong involvement of Municipality personnel.
- Information on the progress of how many Municipalities of Crete have prepared Energy Efficiency plans for their public buildings is not publicly available and is not available to CRES / RDFC. Contact with each Municipality would be required in order to obtain it, and in many cases it may not be easily found, as the plans may have been prepared by external consultants, without strong involvement of Municipality personnel.
- Overall it appears that there is significant potential for improvement of coordination and monitoring of energy transition actions between the different governance levels in the pilot territory (as well as at national level), and there are already tools and

governance structures that have been identified as part of past or ongoing projects, that could be useful to further explore in the context of the ePLANET project.

Spain / Region of Catalonia / Province of Girona

- The majority of the current legal and policy framework related to energy transition is at national level (Government Laws, national plans etc.). At regional level, the Catalan Government approved the Climate Change Law (2017) based on a National Agreement for energy transition, including targets for the improvement of governance.
- There have been delays in transposing the provisions of recent EU Directives (such as recast EPBD, EED etc.) into the national legal and policy framework, thus delays in actually implementing these requirements by the public sector.
- The existing regulatory framework provides technical and administrative incentives regarding self-consumption of electric energy for self-consumers as well as ‘collective prosumers’ thus facilitating the operation of energy communities.
- 201 Municipalities in the Province of Girona are redacting their SECAP and the plans are expected to be submitted to the CoM by end of May 2022.
- Within the ERDF Operative Program for Catalonia, it is foreseen to install 7 biomass boilers, build 15 biomass heat networks and build 2 buildings for forest biomass treatment.

Czech Republic / Zlín Region

- The majority of the current legal and policy framework related to energy transition is at national level (Government Laws, national plans etc.). At regional level, the Zlín Region has developed (2019) an “Energy Action Plan and Energy Efficiency Financing Plan” based on the key pillars of the Regional Energy Strategy, and also a “Regional Action Plan”. The elaboration of the action plan was based on a participatory approach with the involvement of representatives of the Zlín Region, towns and municipalities of the Zlín Region and other local, regional and national important and relevant stakeholders. All stakeholders are directly or indirectly involved in building renovation and energy-efficient building activities, the creation and renovation of district heating and other urban renewal actions in the regions.
- Energy communities are not developed in the Czech Republic, and the main barrier is that the respective legislation and related definition of permissible legal forms of energy communities are not yet in place. There are also no rules set-up for participating in and sharing electricity. A major obstacle to development is also the obligation to have an energy trading license if it is not just a common supply point or

a local distribution system. The adjustment of the tariff structure is also considered a key issue for the willingness of citizens to participate in an energy community. There are however new and existing financial instruments at national level that are anticipated to support energy communities.

- There are no signatories of the Covenant of Mayors at local level in the Zlín Region (EAZK is a supporting partner since 2014), and most of the energy efficiency measures rely on the effectiveness and active support of EAZK to adapt local level policies and goals to the energy transition.
- Overall it appears that there is a margin to improve horizontal governance of energy transition in the Zlín Region. The capacity building of local officers, the deployment of a horizontal governance framework for local authorities, and the deployment of a sharing information platform will foster the multi-level governance of the Region.

Finally, as an overall conclusion, it appears that there is significant potential for improvement of coordination and multi-level governance for energy transition in the participating territories. The outcomes of the present review, including identified existing governance structures and tools, best practices and conclusions drawn, aim to contribute towards this direction as well as to provide useful feedback to the subsequent WP2 tasks of the ePLANET project, such as Task T2.4, where new figures / structures and tools will be proposed to improve energy transition vertical and horizontal governance, adapted to the local context, existing framework and needs of the participating pilot regions.

APPENDIX

T2.2 Template for Information collection

**KAPÉ
CRES**

CENTRE FOR RENEWABLE
ENERGY SOURCES AND SAVING

Template for information collection

In the framework of:

WP2 Governance, Task 2.2 Governance networks

Deliverable D2.2 Report on existing governance structures and list of available tools for the monitoring of ET projects

Task 2.2 Responsible partner: Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES)

WP2 Coordinator: Catalan Energy Institute (ICAEN)

Contributing partner: ...

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1. Introduction

The template serves the purpose of collecting information from the contributing ePLANET partners, that will form the basis for the development of the following ePLANET Deliverable:

D2.2 Report on existing governance structures and list of available tools for the monitoring of Energy Transition projects

in the context of **WP2 Governance, Task 2.2: Governance networks**

Task Responsible partner: CRES

Contributing partners: ICAEN (WP2 Coordinator), CIMNE, FEDARENE, ICLEI, DDGI, RDFC, EAZK

The objective of Task 2.2 is to **gather and analyse requirements and best practices from existing EU or national governance networks and initiatives and from past/ongoing projects** addressing public authorities' Energy Transition (ET), focusing on the following aspects:

- Current **legal and policy framework** related to energy transition in the partners' territories;
- Current **governance figures** (institutionalized structures, designated individuals etc.) that coordinate and monitor energy transition plans and projects, and could be linked to the future 'ePLANET facilitators' (to define within T2.4);
- Current **tools / methodologies / digital platforms** used by public authorities for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects.

The outcomes of this Task will serve to get an overview and better understanding of the current governance framework in the partners' territories, identifying best practices, barriers, lessons learnt from past and ongoing EU and national projects and initiatives. The review will also feed the subsequent WP2 Tasks, where new figures/structures and tools will be proposed, to improve vertical and horizontal governance for energy transition.

To this effect, input from the ePLANET partners is required in the fields described in the following sections of this template.

2. Contributing Partner information

Partner Organisation	
Location (City, Region, Country)	
Short partner profile	
Main role(s) in ePLANET	

3. Template for information collection

3.1 Legal and policy framework for energy transition

Please report the key elements of the current legal and policy framework (at national and / or regional pilot level and / or local level) in your territories, related to energy transition i.e.:

- Current laws for the transposition of the most relevant European Directives related to energy transition (e.g. 2010/31/EU, 2012/27/EU, 2018/844/EU etc.);
- Any specific policies, regulations, or measures adopted for the implementation of the aforementioned legal framework;
- Any existing energy transition plans at national and / or regional pilot level and/or local level in your territories (e.g. National Energy & Climate Plans, regional energy transition plans, local Sustainable Energy & Climate Action Plans etc.).

Please describe the main **objectives** of the provided elements and the **governance level** (national, regional or local) to which each element applies. Please report the **implementation status**, any lack of policies, or possible **barriers** in the implementation of the legal / policy framework.

No. of Element	1
Element of the legal or policy framework (e.g. Law, governmental decision, decree, regulation, directive, plan, etc.).	
Applicability level (national, regional, local)	
Description / key aspects	
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	
References Provide accessible online source (e.g. url) or directly send relevant description document(s) to CRES (*)	

(*) If information is sent to CRES, please limit to 1-2 essential documents that describe the element you consider worth reviewing as part of ePLANET. Information in English, where available, should be preferred.

.....ADD TABLE(S) TO PROVIDE INFORMATION FOR ADDITIONAL ELEMENTS.....

3.2 Governance status in existing EU networks and initiatives

Please describe the governance status in relation to energy transition, in current EU-wide networks and initiatives related to the project objectives, i.e.:

- What are the **governance structures / figures** introduced by these networks, for coordinating and monitoring energy transition plans and actions? These may be either within the networks themselves (e.g. secretariat, council, committee etc.) or within public authorities (e.g. local council, designated personnel etc.);
- Are there any **tools / methodologies / digital platforms** introduced by these networks for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities? If so, what type of information/data is required to be collected and how?

Please describe the main **objectives** of the provided elements and the **implementation status** e.g. progress, expected or achieved impacts, possible barriers etc.

No. of Element	1
Network name	
Network website	
Network logo / 1-2 images (if relevant)	
Number of Members	
Countries coverage	
Description of network	
Introduced governance structure / figure for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	
Introduced tool / methodology / digital platform for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	
References Provide accessible online source (e.g. url) or directly send relevant description document(s) to CRES (*)	

(*) If information is sent to CRES, please limit to 1-2 essential documents that describe the element you consider worth reviewing as part of ePLANET. Information in English, where available, should be preferred.

.....ADD TABLE(S) TO PROVIDE INFORMATION FOR ADDITIONAL ELEMENTS.....

3.3 Governance status within the pilot territories

Please describe the governance status in relation to energy transition in your pilot territories, i.e.:

- What are the **governance structures / figures** coordinating and monitoring energy transition plans and actions in your territories? (i.e. are there any institutionalized structures e.g. Regional or national energy transition committees, boards, etc. or individuals e.g. Region / Municipalities energy manager, CoM regional or Municipal coordinator etc.?). Is there multi-level governance coordination on energy transition between **National level, Regions and Municipalities**?
- Are there any **tools / methodologies / digital platforms** used in your territories for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities? If so, what type of information/data is required to be collected and how?

Please describe the **implementation status** e.g. progress, possible barriers etc.

Pilot territory - (describe)	
Description of governance structure / figure coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	
Description of tools / methodologies / digital platforms for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	
References Provide accessible online source (e.g. url) or directly send relevant description document(s) to CRES (*)	

(*) If information is sent to CRES, please limit to 1-2 essential documents that describe the element you consider worth reviewing as part of ePLANET. Information in English, where available, should be preferred.

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3.4 Best practices from past or ongoing projects

Please describe **best practices on multi-level governance for energy transition** that you have identified from **past or ongoing projects of consortium partners & beyond (national/EU projects)**. This may include:

- **Best practices on introduced governance structures / figures** coordinating and monitoring energy transition plans and actions between **National level, Regions and Municipalities** (i.e. institutionalized structures or individuals etc.);
- **Best practices on produced tools/ methodologies / digital platforms** for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities.

Please describe the main **objectives** of the provided elements and the **implementation status** e.g. progress, expected or achieved impacts, possible barriers etc.

No. of Element	1
Project full title/acronym	
Funding Programme	
Project website	
Project logo / 1-2 images (if relevant)	
Project status (ongoing / completed)	
Introduced governance structure / figure for coordinating energy transition plans and actions (e.g. secretariat, council, committee, designated individual etc.)	
Introduced tool /methodology / digital platform for multi-level governance coordination and monitoring of ET projects by public authorities	
Implementation status (progress; barriers; delays)	
References Provide accessible online source (e.g. url) or directly send relevant description document(s) to CRES (*)	

(*) If information is sent to CRES, please limit to 1-2 essential documents that describe the element you consider worth reviewing as part of ePLANET. Information in English, where available, should be preferred.

.....ADD TABLE(S) TO PROVIDE INFORMATION FOR ADDITIONAL ELEMENTS.....